

D3.4 OVERALL FINDINGS, RECOMMENDATIONS AND CONCLUSIONS FROM THE CASE STUDIES

Work package	WP3 Definition and analysis of relevant case studies for the circular bioeconomy
Task	T3.4 Analysis of findings and derivation of main conclusions and recommendations
Due date	30 April 2025
Submission date	12 January 2026
Deliverable lead	Wageningen Research
Version	1.0
Authors	Berien Elbersen (WR), Iris Vural Gursel (WR), Heleen Ballemans (WR) Gülşah Yılan (UNIT), Luana Ladu (BAM), Mariam Rasheed (BAM), Joris Van Acker (UGENT), Tobi Hallez (UGENT), Laura García Laverde (DBFZ), Janire Clavell (TECNALIA) Alireza Khosravi (UNIT), Majid Zaeemi (UNIT), Carlota Garcia Diaz (CIRCE)
Contributors	All partners
Reviewers	All partners

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
0.1	21.03.2025	Draft structure of the deliverable	WR
0.2	15.04.2025	Complete draft ready for review	WR, UNIT, BAM, UGENT, , DBFZ
0.3	18.04.2025	Reviewer’s comments and edits	All partners
0.4	22.04.2025	Final draft after implementing edits/comments	WR
1.0	24.04.2025	Final check and submission	UNIT
2.0	12.01.2026	Format revision upon the PO’s comments and resubmission	UNIT

Abstract

The transition from linear fossil-based systems to circular and bio-based systems represents an opportunity and a suitable pathway for achieving several SDGs. Indeed, circular bio-based systems depict a great opportunity to reconcile sustainable long-term growth with environmental protection through the prudent use of renewable resources for industrial purposes. This needed transition is a complex process, which does not simply require innovative technologies from the supply-side, but also societal transformations based on a multi-actor process. The circular bioeconomy meta-sector may be a good candidate to put forward a new economic model, which requires transformative policies, purposeful innovation, access to finance, risk-taking capacity as well as new and sustainable business models and markets. However, a critical assessment of the environmental, social, and economic impacts of the current linear fossil-based economy, as well as of the improvement potential associated with circular bio-based systems, is needed to underpin the identification of policy priorities. Bearing this in mind, SUSTRACK is a three-year project aimed at supporting policymakers in their efforts to develop sustainable pathways to replace fossil and carbon-intensive systems with sustainable circular and bio-based systems (at the EU and regional scale), contributing to achieving the European Green Deal's objectives. This will be done by: identifying environmental, economic and social limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy; improving existing assessment methodologies; assessing the environmental, social and economic impacts of the EU's current linear fossil-based economy; comparing multiple transition scenarios focusing on the most carbon intensive sectors; identifying priorities according to scenarios analysed in the project and develop guidelines and policy recommendations.

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union under project number 101081823. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Copyright notice: © 2022 - 2025 SUSTRACK Consortium

Deliverable information		
Nature of the deliverable:		R*
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g., web	x
CL	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO	Confidential to SUSTRACK project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

SUSTRACK Consortium:

#	Participant Organisation Name	Short Name	Country
1	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI ROMA UNITELMA SAPIENZA	UNIT	IT
2	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	WR	NL
3	KNOWLEDGE SRL	KE	IT
4	PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	PC	SK
5	DBFZ DEUTSCHES BIOMASSEFORSCHUNGSZENTRUM GEMEINNUTZIGE GMBH	DBFZ	DE
6	UNIVERSITEIT GENT	UGENT	BE
7	FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION	TECNALIA	ES
8	FVA SAS DI LOUIS FERRINI & C	FVA	IT
9	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI FERRARA	UNIFE	IT
10	BUNDESANSTALT FUER MATERIALFORSCHUNG UND - PRUEFUNG	BAM	DE
11	FUNDACION CIRCE CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION DE RECURSOS Y CONSUMOS ENERGETICOS	CIRCE	ES

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The goal of achieving net-zero emissions by the European economy by 2050 demands a shift from linear, fossil-based systems to circular, bio-based systems. This transition is vital for meeting the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals and reconciling environmental protection with sustainable growth. However, the complexity of the transition relies on societal transformations, cutting-edge technologies, and multi-actor processes, requiring a new economic framework and policy priorities that align with the European Green Deal.

This report presents the SUSTRACK T3.4 results on case study assessments. In T3.1, 10 case studies were selected; later, an additional case study was included. In T2.1, the SUSTRACK - Circular Bioeconomy Monitoring System was developed. In T3.2, validation of this monitoring system was carried out, and guidelines for the implementation of the case study assessment were prepared. For this, the monitoring system was tested, and the most relevant and suitable indicators were identified for each case study. Additionally, guidelines were made for mapping stakeholders and policy instruments, and for the collection of information and data for the case study analysis. T3.3 builds on the work carried out in T3.2. The guidance and methodology for case study analysis, as set out in D3.2, are followed for the assessment of the 11 selected case studies. Also, the analysis of indicators that was carried out as part of the consistency check forms the foundation for this work. Additionally, in T3.3, stakeholder engagements were used in gathering input for the case studies. This includes, besides dedicated interviews with targeted stakeholders input gathered at the INSPIRE and DESIGN co-creation workshops. The findings from these engagements were categorised into three dimensions: market, policy, and sustainability. The outcomes from these case study assessments serve as input for other WPs, especially for WP4 for the analysis of each sector by means of the Green Economy Model and for WP5 for the identification of policy priorities, the definition of policy actions based on discussions on challenges and opportunities.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Introduction	12
2	Construction sector	14
2.1	Short description of the sector and the 3 case studies	14
2.2	Main challenges and opportunities in the transition to a CBBE in the construction sector 14	
2.3	Recommendations and good practice examples.....	19
2.4	Policy recommendations to stimulate transition and enhance resource efficiency	22
3	Textile sector	28
3.1	Short description of the sector and the 3 case studies	28
3.2	Main challenges and opportunities in the transition to a CBBE in the textiles sector ...	28
3.3	Recommendations and good practice examples.....	32
3.4	Policy recommendations to stimulate transition and enhance resource efficiency	34
4	Chemical sector	40
4.1	Short description of the sector and the 2 case studies	40
4.2	Main challenges and opportunities in the transition to a CBBE in the chemical sector..	41
4.3	Recommendations and good practice examples	43
4.4	Policy recommendations to stimulate transition and enhance resource efficiency	45
5	Plastics sector	50
5.1	Short description of the sector and the 3 case studies	50
5.2	Main challenges and opportunities in the transition to a CBBE in the plastics sector ...	51
5.3	Recommendations and good practice examples.....	54
5.4	Policy recommendations to stimulate transition and enhance resource efficiency	55
6	Overall conclusions and recommendations	59
6.1	Overarching challenges	59
6.2	Overarching policy recommendations.....	62
	References.....	65

Appendix 1 Overview type of policy instruments68

Appendix 2 Overview of principles of the Circular Bio-based Economy to which policy instruments can contribute69

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. Selected case studies and corresponding sectors	12
Table 2 Overview of policy instruments identified to tackle barriers and/or stimulate transition to CBBE	23
Table 3 Overview of policy instruments identified to tackle barriers and/or stimulate transition or both.....	35
Table 4 Overview of policy instruments identified to tackle barriers and/or stimulate transition to CBBE	45
Table 5 Overview of policy instruments identified to tackle barriers and/or stimulate CBBE transition.....	55

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Meaning
AGEC law	Loi Anti-Gaspillage pour une Économie Circulaire
BBCP	Bio-based , Biodegradable and Compostable Plastics
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
CBBE	Circular Bio-based Economy
CBBM	Circular, Bio-based Construction Materials
CBAM	Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism
CCU	CO ₂ Capture and Utilisation
CEAP	Circular Economy Action Plan
CA	Cellulose Acetate
CLT	Cross-laminated timber
CPR	Construction Products Regulation
CRCF	Carbon Removals and Carbon Framing
CSS	Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability
DG	Directorate General
DPP	Digital Product Passport
EC	European Commission
EoL	End-of-Life
EPBP	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EPD	Environmental Product Declaration
EPR	Extended Producer Responsibility
ESPR	Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation
ETS	Emission Trading System
EU	European Union
EUTR	EU Timber Regulation

ELVR	End-of-life Vehicles Regulation
GCD	Green Claims Directive
GHG	Greenhouse gas
GWP	Global warming potential
HMCFs	Human-made cellulosic fibres
LCA	Life cycle analysis
LULCF	Land Use and Land use Change and Forestry
MESG	Methanol Sector Group
MEG	Monoethylene glycol
MMCFs	Man-made cellulosic fibres
MPW	Municipal plastic waste
MSW	Municipal solid waste
NEB	New European Bauhaus initiative
NECP	National Energy and Climate Plan
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
PET	Polyethylene terephthalate
PHA	Polyhydroxyalkanoates
PLA	Polylactic acid
PP	Polypropylene
PPRW	Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation
PPWD	Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive
R&D	Research and Development
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restrictions of Chemicals
RED	Renewable Energy Directive

RES	Renewable Energies Share
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SME	Small Medium sized Entreprise
SOC	Soil organic carbon
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) framework
SUPD	Single-Use Plastics Directive
TRL	Technology readiness level
UCO	Used cooked oil
UN	United Nations
VAT	Value Added Tax
VOC	Volatile Organic Compounds
WFD	Waste Framework Directive
WLC	Whole Life Carbon framework
WMA	Waste Management Act
WP	Work package

1 INTRODUCTION

The SUSTRACK project adopts a bottom-up approach to the development and validation of key project outputs (including the SUSTRACK - Circular Bioeconomy Monitoring System developed in WP2) by testing them against real case studies. In T3.1, 10 case studies were selected (Table 1). Later on, another case study was added on cellulose acetate (see Table 1). They belong to four sectors that face critical challenges within the current linear system: (a) the construction sector; (b) the textile sector; (c) the (fine) chemical sector; and (d) the plastics sector.

Table 1. Selected case studies and corresponding sectors

Sector	Case study
Construction	Cross-laminated timber
Construction	Biochar as an additive in concrete
Construction	Hemp insulation
Textile	Recycled carded wool from Prato, Italy
Textile	Man-made cellulosic fibres, like Lyocell
Textile	Latxa sheep wool from the Basque Country of Spain
Chemical	Waste to methanol
Chemical	Bio-MEG, bio-MPG, and renewable functional fillers from wood
Plastics	Polylactic acid (PLA)
Plastics	Polypropylene (PP) from used cooking oil (UCO)
Plastics	Cellulose acetate

An extensive description and analysis of all 11 case studies was done in Tasks 3.2 and 3.3, and this was reported in D3.3. It covers for each case study, information on the value chain, the conversion process from biomass to product, and its market, the most relevant stakeholders involved in the value chain and their mapping in terms of their power and interest to drive change and influence the further transition toward more circular bio-based processes in the four sectors. Also, policies of relevance per value chain were identified, and information is provided on whether it is stimulating or acting as a barrier to the development of that value chain. Subsequently, an overview is provided of the most relevant indicators for each case study for monitoring and proving the circularity and sustainability of the value chain per case study. These indicators cover three categories, which are environmental/circular, economic and social. For the selected relevant indicators per case study, it was reviewed whether information and data are available to assess the indicator and where data and information gaps are. The indicators were also used to provide insights into the sustainability performance of the value chain, as well as the research gaps existing in performing sustainability monitoring. Finally, it should be mentioned that the case study and sectoral insights reported in D3.3 were based on reviews of scientific and grey literature, websites and on outcomes of former SUSTRACK stakeholder workshops and interviews done with specific stakeholders.

The objective of T3.4, which is presented in this report, takes the results generated per case study in the former tasks and deliverables, and presents the main findings, conclusions and recommendations derived from these activities. These are presented for the four sectors in focus.

The report is structured as follows: Chapters 2 to 5 present the main findings, conclusions and recommendations per sector (construction, textile, chemical and plastics). Each chapter starts with a short description of the key characteristics of the case studies per sector. This is followed by the main findings concerning the main challenges and opportunities identified for the transition to a circular and bio-based economy (CBBE). The third sub-section of each section makes recommendations for good example practices for the sector that help the transition, and the last section discusses the policy approaches and instruments that could further enhance the transition in the future. The final Chapter 6 ends with an overview of the main conclusions and recommendations overall all sectors and case studies.

2 CONSTRUCTION SECTOR

2.1 Short description of the sector and the 3 case studies

The construction industry is a cornerstone of the European Union's economy, providing approximately 18 million direct jobs and contributing around 9% of the EU's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) (European Commission, 2020). As one of the largest industrial sectors in Europe, it plays a vital role in economic development, employment, and innovation. However, the building and construction sector also has a significant environmental impact. It accounts for nearly 50% of all raw materials extracted in the EU and is responsible for over 35% of the total waste generated (European Commission, 2020; Eurostat, 2021). Furthermore, the extraction of materials, manufacturing of construction products, and building activities contribute to approximately 5-12% of total national greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions across Member States (European Commission, 2022). In the context of the European Green Deal, which aims to achieve climate neutrality by 2050, the construction industry is identified as a strategic sector for decarbonization. Its transformation holds immense potential for enhancing material efficiency, reducing embodied carbon, and scaling up the use of sustainable and circular solutions, including bio-based materials. As such, the sector is central to realising the EU's climate and environmental goals.

For the construction sector, three case studies were selected, described, and analysed in detail. Each case study highlights innovative solutions that can significantly reduce resource use and GHG emissions in construction and the built environment. While full results are available in SUSTRACK D3.3, the focus here is on the main conclusions and recommendations. The first case study examines Cross-Laminated Timber (CLT), an engineered wood product made by stacking and glueing multiple layers of lumber boards at perpendicular angles. This structure provides high tensile and compressive strength, making CLT suitable for floors, walls, roofs, and stairs, including multi-story wood buildings. The second case study focuses on biochar, a carbon-rich byproduct of biomass pyrolysis. Recognised under the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification (CRCF) Regulation, biochar offers long-term carbon storage benefits. In construction, it can be used as a filler or partial cement substitute in concrete, contributing to lower emissions. The third case study explores hemp-based insulation. Industrial hemp serves as a renewable feedstock for thermal and acoustic insulation materials like hemp wool and hempcrete. These products provide sustainable alternatives that improve building energy efficiency while reducing environmental impact.

2.2 Main challenges and opportunities in the transition to a CBBE in the construction sector

The challenges for the transition of the mainly linear and strong fossil-based sector towards a more circular bio-based construction sector are described in this section. These are based on the perspectives derived from the detailed analysis of the three case studies and the different insights obtained during the SUSTRACK DESIGN and IMPLEMENT workshops with stakeholders, both specific to the case studies and the wider EU construction sector.

The challenges can be categorised according to market, sustainability and policy aspects.

Market dimension challenges

Lack of Harmonised Standards for Bio-based Construction Products

The absence of harmonised standards for construction products, particularly for newer bio-based materials such as CLT, hemp, and biochar, is a significant barrier to creating a truly unified European single market. Currently, these products must comply with varying national standards across EU member states, which increases both administrative and compliance costs. This fragmentation especially affects smaller producers, who often bear the greatest burdens due to limited resources. Overlapping regulations and inconsistencies also create inefficiencies that slow down market entry and innovation. This lack of uniformity undermines investment, limits sales, and hampers the widespread adoption of bio-based materials as reliable, one-to-one replacements for traditional fossil-based construction products. Harmonised technical specifications, which define how to test and communicate the performance of construction products in areas such as fire resistance, thermal conductivity, and sound insulation, would provide a common language across the EU. Without these standards, progress in the sector is significantly slowed. In addition, many existing standards are outdated and fail to reflect current innovations in bio-based construction. As a result, bio-based products are often evaluated using inappropriate criteria, putting them at a disadvantage in areas such as fire performance, thermal efficiency, life cycle assessments (including biogenic carbon and carbon storage), and carbon offsetting.

Cost-Related Challenges

Cost remains a major obstacle to the adoption of circular, bio-based construction materials (CBBMs). The construction sector continues to experience rising material prices, and for bio-based alternatives, these cost pressures are often intensified. Higher initial costs may come from the materials themselves or additional labour associated with installation. For example, fire safety regulations may require bio-based materials to include extra protective layers, which increases both material and labour costs. CLT, in particular, carries higher upfront costs due to its precise, pre-manufactured panels and the relatively expensive raw material. However, the prefabricated nature of CLT can streamline on-site construction, resulting in time and labour savings. Its adaptability makes it especially useful for complex designs. Nevertheless, the overall cost of projects using CLT is not always lower than those using traditional materials such as steel or concrete. Mechanisms like carbon credits or tax incentives could help make CLT, biochar, and hemp insulation more competitive against fossil-based alternatives.

Public sector projects also face financing challenges. Faster construction times with timber and other bio-based materials can clash with payment schedules based on slower concrete construction, creating cash flow issues for projects that move ahead more quickly. Insurance remains another issue, as concerns around the fire resistance of bio-based buildings affect premiums and access. Access to capital for developing and marketing new bio-based products is limited. Investors and financial institutions often perceive these materials as high-risk due to uncertainty around market demand, performance, and regulation. This hesitation restricts innovation and market growth. Yet, when considering a building's entire life cycle, bio-based materials often outperform traditional options. They offer significantly improved energy efficiency, especially in insulation applications. Studies show that agglomerated cork (Barreca et al., 2019) and hempcrete (Bennai et al., 2022) can reduce operational energy consumption by 75% and 16%, respectively, compared to brick used in building envelopes (Le et al., 2024). These savings contribute to lower life cycle costs, making bio-based products more viable in the long

run. Furthermore, not all bio-based materials come with higher upfront costs; some are already competitive with traditional materials.

Workforce and Skills Challenges

A lack of technical knowledge and practical experience within the construction industry continues to hinder the transition to a CBBE. Designers, architects, and contractors often lack the training, confidence, or motivation to switch from conventional materials to bio-based alternatives. Since these professionals play a central role in determining which materials are used in building and renovation projects, their hesitancy significantly slows adoption.

Biomass Supply and Material Availability

The supply of bio-based materials and the biomass needed to produce them remains a challenge. For biochar, securing consistent, high-quality feedstock at predictable costs is difficult. Additionally, subsidies and rising demand for biomass in the energy sector distort the market, reducing availability for construction use. In the hemp sector, the lack of industrial-scale processing facilities within the EU limits growth. Without sufficient infrastructure, production costs remain high, and supply chains stay inefficient. This bottleneck hinders the adoption of hemp-based products across the construction industry. Limited material availability, especially of locally produced options, reflects the small market size for bio-based construction materials. This restricts access to economies of scale and slows down the technological learning curve necessary to reduce costs and improve performance. As a result, bio-based materials remain less competitive compared to their conventional counterparts.

Sustainability dimension challenges

Mindset and Perception Challenges

Bio-based and circular construction materials continue to face major challenges due to limited knowledge, low awareness, and common misconceptions about their performance, durability, and sustainability in the construction sector. Traditional construction education and practices are still largely centred on fossil-based materials. As a result, awareness of alternative, eco-friendly solutions remains low, and progress toward more sustainable practices is slowed. Cross-laminated timber, for example, is often misunderstood. Concerns about timber's durability, fire safety, and environmental impact persist, particularly with regard to the sustainability of wood harvesting. These concerns are often based on outdated perceptions and a lack of awareness about Europe's high forest management standards, which focus on biodiversity conservation, sustainable harvesting, and ecosystem restoration. This lack of understanding limits the acceptance of timber as a renewable and environmentally friendly construction material. Similarly, industrial hemp suffers from limited awareness and is still affected by stigma due to its association with cannabis. Although industrial hemp does not have psychoactive properties, misconceptions about its safety and cultivation continue to hinder its use in construction. Uncertainty about regulations, the challenges of growing hemp as an agricultural crop, and a lack of clarity around its benefits all contribute to slow adoption. The construction sector's conservative and decentralised nature also creates structural obstacles to change. Many industry professionals lack the knowledge, skills, and confidence to adopt new materials, and this often leads to resistance. In some cases, there is outright unwillingness to shift away from familiar fossil-based products. Without a broader change in mindset, it will be difficult to advance bio-based construction at scale. A cultural shift is needed

to embrace these materials in both new builds and renovation projects, and to support a wider transition toward a circular bioeconomy in construction.

Demolition Waste, Recycling, and Reuse

The construction sector is currently the largest generator of waste in the European Union, with demolition waste representing the biggest share. When construction products reach the end of their life, they typically become waste. To move away from this linear approach and toward a circular model, it is essential to manage building materials more effectively at the end of their life cycle. This includes implementing systems for collection, sorting, reuse, recycling, and material recovery. For bio-based construction products, proper end-of-life management is especially important to prevent them from ending up in landfills or incinerators. Although products like hemp insulation are advertised as being fully recyclable, their recyclability is often limited in practice. Key challenges include the lack of effective dismantling practices, the absence of organised sorting and collection at demolition sites, and the small overall quantity of bio-based waste. Together, these issues highlight a significant gap in recovery methods for bio-based materials.

Another contributing factor is that many buildings, both old and new, have not been designed with disassembly in mind. This makes it more difficult to recover materials for reuse or recycling. In addition, there is often a lack of accurate data on the materials used in older buildings. This makes it hard to predict the types of waste produced during demolition and increases the risk of encountering hazardous substances that cannot be recycled. Improving the recyclability and recovery of bio-based materials requires new design strategies, better data collection, and investments in circular infrastructure throughout the construction industry.

Life Cycle Assessment of Bio-based vs Traditional Materials

There are still many uncertainties when it comes to assessing the full life cycle carbon footprint of CLT and other bio-based materials. Key challenges include accounting for biogenic carbon, predicting service life, estimating maintenance needs, modelling greenhouse gas flows over time, and determining the impact of end-of-life treatment options. The use of CLT influences both carbon emissions and carbon storage across its life cycle. Its environmental impact depends on several factors, such as the sustainability of forest management, the efficiency of wood processing, transportation distances, and disposal or reuse strategies at the end of its service life. While CLT and other wood products have great potential for carbon storage, more research is needed to accurately evaluate their net climate benefits across all life cycle stages. Bio-based materials also offer broader environmental advantages. These include carbon sequestration, lower embodied carbon, and improvements in energy efficiency. However, current life cycle assessment (LCA) frameworks are not designed to fully capture the benefits of these materials. As a result, bio-based products often appear less competitive when compared to traditional construction materials like concrete or steel. To better reflect the environmental value of bio-based solutions, updated LCA methods are needed. These frameworks should account for renewable inputs, carbon storage potential, and reuse possibilities. By incorporating these factors, it will be easier to demonstrate the true benefits of circular, bio-based materials and increase their competitiveness in the market.

Policy dimension challenges

Policy, Standards, and Regulatory Gaps

Both the case studies and the DESIGN and IMPLEMENT workshops highlighted the need for stronger policy guidance related to norms, standards, and regulations in the construction sector. Existing building norms and standards—both at the EU and national levels—are often unfavourable toward bio-based materials. These standards were developed primarily for conventional construction materials, creating systemic barriers that limit the adoption of innovative, sustainable alternatives. Because these regulations prioritize traditional materials, they often overlook or inadequately accommodate the unique properties and performance benefits of bio-based materials such as timber, hemp, and biochar. This misalignment hinders certification, slows down market integration, and creates an uneven playing field. Bio-based materials differ significantly from geo- and fossil-based ones in terms of behaviour, environmental impact, and function. Yet, current regulations rarely reflect these differences, making it harder for such products to meet standard requirements and gain widespread acceptance.

CLT and timber-based construction: Fire safety regulations present a notable barrier to the adoption of timber-based construction. Many of these regulations are based on outdated assumptions and do not reflect the advancements in engineered wood technologies or fire-resistant treatments. As a result, they restrict the broader application of sustainable timber products like CLT, despite their proven performance and environmental benefits.

Hemp and other bio-based Insulation: Standardised testing methods for assessing thermal performance do not adequately capture the hygro-thermal behaviour of insulation materials such as hemp, hempcrete and other bio-based insulation materials. These methods focus on static thermal conductivity and overlook the material's ability to regulate moisture, which plays a crucial role in its insulation performance over time. This leads to an incomplete understanding of how bio-based insulation performs under real-world conditions.

Biochar in Concrete: Biochar-based construction products are also held back by a lack of supporting standards. Without adequate technical frameworks, innovative concrete products incorporating biochar struggle to gain traction and legitimacy in the market.

Regional Differences and Inconsistencies

The construction landscape is further complicated by regulatory discrepancies across EU countries. Industrial hemp, for example, faces differing legal restrictions and uncertainties between regions, which severely limit its adoption as a building material and slow down the development of hemp-based innovations. Additionally, the absence of harmonised Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) across Europe undermines efforts to assess and compare the environmental impact of different materials. This fragmentation creates confusion for manufacturers, investors, and consumers alike. Without harmonised EU standards, many hemp-based products cannot obtain CE marking, a critical certification for product acceptance and use within the EU. As a result, market access is limited. Nonetheless, efforts are underway to secure European Technical Assessments and promote CE marking at both national and EU levels. Achieving this would help standardise the approval process and foster greater acceptance of hemp-based materials across the continent.

Incentives and Public Sector Support

Currently, the construction sector is not required to prioritise the use of sustainable or circular materials. The lack of government mandates and incentives for adopting bio-based construction products significantly contributes to their low implementation rate. While initiatives like the EU Renovation Wave have successfully improved the energy efficiency of buildings, thus lowering

their operational carbon footprint, less attention has been paid to reducing embodied carbon through material choices. This presents an opportunity to extend the impact of such programs by integrating bio-based and circular construction materials into renovation and new-build projects. Public support, including policy incentives and promotional efforts, can help mitigate the higher initial costs associated with some bio-based products. These measures would reduce financial hesitation among stakeholders and accelerate the shift toward sustainable construction practices. Ultimately, the findings point to the critical role of governments in enabling systemic change by updating regulations, harmonising standards, and offering tangible incentives for circular bio-based materials.

2.3 Recommendations and good practice examples

Overall, the three case studies clearly serve as good practice examples of production systems that support the transition toward a more sustainable construction sector. The analysis of these case studies, along with insights from SUSTRACK DESIGN and IMPLEMENT conferences, yielded numerous specific recommendations and good practice examples to help overcome the various barriers previously discussed.

The case studies are examples of good practices:

The **CLT case study** presents a comprehensive set of recommendations and good practices aimed at accelerating the transition toward a more sustainable construction sector through the wider adoption of bio-based materials. A key recommendation is the revamping of building norms and regulations to acknowledge and support the use of materials like timber, recognising their structural performance, safety standards, and significant environmental benefits. This regulatory shift would not only promote innovation and the development of new materials but also reduce reliance on carbon-intensive resources, supporting the broader move toward a circular and low-carbon economy. Another critical aspect is the need for clear, comprehensive, and directly actionable governmental guidelines on assessing embodied carbon in construction materials, which would enhance transparency and consistency across the industry. In parallel, it is essential to incorporate the assessment of biogenic carbon-accounting for both the sequestration potential and the embodied emissions of materials such as timber through dynamic LCAs and improved land use indicators that reflect evolving land management practices. Encouraging a cultural shift toward a bio-based mindset across the sector is also vital, as it would help normalise the use of renewable, bio-based, and low-carbon alternatives, spurring innovation and reducing environmental impact. Supporting further research into bio-based adhesives is another area of focus, as this can lead to the development of non-toxic, high-performance bonding solutions that align with sustainable construction goals. To incentivise the adoption of such materials, governments could offer tax benefits, introduce green taxation on construction materials or offer financial support for producers of bio-based construction materials, and introduce a certification framework for carbon removals that rewards the carbon sequestration benefit of bio-based products. The subsidies for biomass for bioenergy should also be reduced to ensure that biomass from our forests is used for long-lasting products, as currently over 50% of harvested woody biomass is used for energy generation (Camia et al., 2018). Introducing cascading principles for wood prioritises efficient and sustainable use of wood by extending its lifecycle through multiple stages, with energy recovering being the last stage after primary use, reuse and recycling. The establishment of standardized European-wide norms and CE-marked EPDs would further harmonize sustainability assessments and practices across member states, facilitating fair competition and broader implementation. Additional policy measures, such as shifting regulatory emphasis from fire resistance to fire reaction—focusing on properties like combustibility and

smoke production—would provide a more accurate safety assessment of bio-based materials. Meanwhile, implementing restrictions on the export of unprocessed timber could stimulate local processing, add value within the EU, support job creation, and reduce environmental impacts related to transport. Collectively, these measures form a holistic strategy to overcome existing barriers, support systemic change, and unlock the full potential of CLT and other bio-based materials in driving a more sustainable and resilient construction industry.

To support the integration of **biochar** into sustainable construction and climate strategies, it is essential to shift from recipe-based standards to performance-based standards under frameworks like the Construction Products Regulation (CPR). This would allow greater flexibility and innovation in using biochar across different applications. Aligning biochar practices with broader EU initiatives, such as the EU Emissions Trading System, the CRCF Regulation, the EU Green Deal, the EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Activities, and Sustainable Carbon Cycles, is crucial for recognising its role in carbon sequestration and climate mitigation. Incorporating robust carbon accounting mechanisms will ensure that the climate benefits of biochar are accurately measured, verified, and integrated into policy and market incentives, further encouraging its adoption as a valuable tool in the transition to a low-carbon, circular economy.

The **hemp insulation case study** underscores the need to revise current thermal performance testing standards to better reflect the unique hygrothermal and hygroscopic properties of bio-based materials such as hemp insulation and hempcrete. Traditional testing often overlooks the impact of moisture regulation on long-term thermal efficiency, and updating these methods would ensure more accurate evaluations. Equally important is addressing public misconceptions about industrial hemp through education and awareness campaigns, highlighting its sustainability, versatility, and potential in construction. Reducing regulatory and production barriers across Europe is essential to unlocking hemp's full value as a sustainable resource. Promoting hemp in crop rotation systems offers additional environmental benefits, such as improved soil health, reduced erosion, and enhanced biodiversity, while also supporting economically viable farming alternatives. The case also emphasises the importance of focusing on long-term, future-proof construction solutions that prioritise sustainability, adaptability, and resilience. A key recommendation is the need to support the entire bio-based supply chain more effectively, from the cultivation of raw materials to processing, manufacturing, and distribution. Strengthening this chain involves investment in infrastructure, research, and technology that improves efficiency, quality control, and scalability. It also means fostering collaboration between farmers, processors, manufacturers, and end-users to create a cohesive ecosystem that encourages innovation and ensures reliable market access. This integrated, systems-based approach not only promotes environmental sustainability but also stimulates economic growth, supports rural development, and builds resilience against supply disruptions. Encouraging local procurement within this supply chain further amplifies its benefits by reducing transportation-related emissions, supporting regional economies, and reinforcing circular production models. Notably, market awareness and interest in hemp-based construction materials have grown significantly in recent years among end users, architects, and developers, signalling the potential for a major shift toward greener building practices and the mainstream adoption of hemp as a key component in sustainable development.

Recommendations from the case studies:

Overarching recommendations to improve sustainable practices in the textile sector are summarised along the following lines:

- **Establish Harmonised European Norms and Standards**

Developing comprehensive and harmonised European norms for construction and material use is essential for achieving regulatory coherence across EU member states. Such standardisation would establish uniform criteria for sustainability assessments, material performance evaluation, and compliance mechanisms. By reducing regulatory fragmentation, it would simplify cross-border collaboration, enhance market transparency, and promote fair competition. Moreover, it would provide a stable and predictable framework for innovation, thereby accelerating the uptake of sustainable and bio-based construction practices throughout Europe.

- **Adapt Regulations to the Specificities of Bio-Based Materials**

Regulatory frameworks must be adapted to account for the specific environmental, thermal, and structural characteristics of bio-based construction materials. Unlike conventional materials, bio-based alternatives offer distinct advantages, including carbon sequestration, renewability, and compatibility with circular economy principles that are often underrepresented in existing regulations. Integrating these attributes into policy and assessment criteria would facilitate more equitable regulatory treatment, stimulate technological and design innovation, and support the broader integration of bio-based materials into conventional construction systems and standards.

- **Expand Education, Training, and Certification in Bio-Based Construction**

Expanding bio-based construction education and training is essential for accelerating the adoption of sustainable building practices. Comprehensive programs that equip architects, builders, and other industry professionals with the knowledge and skills to work with bio-based materials will help bridge the current expertise gap. Investing in specialised training initiatives, apprenticeships, and certification programs will ensure a skilled workforce capable of driving innovation and promoting environmentally friendly construction solutions.

- **Foster Social and Industry Acceptance Through Awareness and Engagement**

Facilitating broader acceptance of bio-based materials necessitates strategic and evidence-based interventions aimed at addressing prevailing scepticism and misconceptions within both professional and public domains. This includes the systematic dissemination of empirical data on the long-term performance, environmental benefits, and economic viability of such materials, supported by well-documented case studies and pilot projects. Stakeholder engagement through targeted outreach, demonstration initiatives, and structured educational programmes is essential to build trust and promote behavioural and institutional change. Additionally, the integration of bio-based materials into green public procurement frameworks can serve as a powerful policy lever, signalling market confidence, reducing perceived risk, and accelerating their mainstream adoption within the construction sector.

- **Promote Systems Thinking and Life Cycle Design Approaches**

The complexity of sustainable building design demands a shift toward systems thinking that accounts for the entire life cycle of buildings, from material sourcing and construction to use,

renovation, and end-of-life. This requires the development of standardised LCA tools, material passports, and collaborative design methodologies to balance trade-offs and optimise environmental and social outcomes throughout a building's lifespan.

- **Strengthen the Entire Bio-Based Supply Chain**

A holistic approach to supporting the entire bio-based supply chain from raw material cultivation and processing to manufacturing, distribution, and end-use is essential for establishing resilient, efficient, and scalable sustainable construction systems. Strengthening each stage of the value chain through targeted investments, the development of dedicated infrastructure, and coherent policy frameworks can significantly improve material quality, ensure supply chain reliability, and stimulate innovation. Such an integrated strategy not only enhances the environmental performance of construction practices but also generates economic value, fosters rural development, and accelerates the transition toward a circular and low-carbon built environment.

- **Leverage Carbon Pricing to Incentivise Low-Carbon Materials**

Carbon pricing instruments such as carbon taxes, green taxation, the Carbon Farming Initiative, and emissions trading schemes can act as effective indirect incentives for the uptake of low-carbon, bio-based construction materials by internalising the external environmental costs associated with carbon-intensive alternatives. By assigning a financial value to greenhouse gas emissions, these mechanisms enhance the market competitiveness of renewable and circular material solutions. However, their efficacy depends on robust design, consistent implementation, and integration within a comprehensive policy framework that addresses structural barriers and ensures an equitable transition towards a more sustainable and climate-resilient construction sector.

2.4 Policy recommendations to stimulate transition and enhance resource efficiency

In the former sections, some recommendations were already made in relation to policy measures that can be taken to stimulate the transition to a more circular and sustainable construction sector in the EU. In the current section, we present in greater detail the policy instruments already identified in the case studies as good practice examples, followed by a discussion of policy instruments that can be implemented in the near future and for which potentially details are already being worked out by the EU and national governments. This section also links to the work done in WP5 of SUSTRACK, where policies have been extensively reviewed and detailed policy recommendations are produced, taking account of extensive reviews of literature, several exchanges with stakeholders in the DEPLOY workshops and through a survey consultation.

An overview of the good policy examples and the recommended new policy instruments is presented in Table 2. The policy instruments are linked to the challenges for the transition they address and that were discussed in the former section, and also to the CBBE targets they contribute to (see Appendix 2).

Table 2 Overview of policy instruments identified to tackle barriers and/or stimulate transition to CBBE

Policy instrument	Existing Good example instrument or proposed or recommended policy instrument?	Type of instrument (direct regulation, market based instrument, or other) (see Appendix 1)	Challenge addressed	Contribution to CBBE target (see Appendix 2)
Construction Products Regulation (CPR)	Existing instrument	Direct regulation	1) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market 2) Lack of transparency 3) Lack of organization of end-of-life treatment to facilitate recycling 4) Integration of Sustainability Metrics	1)Improve resource efficiency
Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD)	Existing instrument	Direct regulation	1) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market 2) Lack of transparenc	1)Improve resource efficiency 2)Reduce GHG emissions
Circular Economy Action Plan	Existing initiative	Strategic framework and regulatory directives	1) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market 2) Lack of transparency 3) Lack of organization of end-of-life treatment to facilitate recyclin	1)Improve resource efficiency 2)Reduce GHG emissions 3)Decoupling
EU Climate Law	Existing good example instrument	Strategic framework and regulatory directives	1) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market 2) Lack of transparency 3) Lack of organization of end-of-life treatment to facilitate recyclin	1)Improve resource efficiency 2)Reduce GHG emissions 3)Decoupling
New European Bauhaus	Existing initiative	Policy framework and financial incentives	1) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market 2) Insufficient Incentives 3) Mindset Shift	1)Improve resource efficiency 2)Reduce GHG emissions 3)Decoupling
Renovation Wave Initiative	Existing initiative	Policy framework and financial incentives	1) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market	1)Improve resource efficiency 2)Reduce GHG emissions
Strategy for a Sustainable Built Environment, Level(s)	Existing initiative	Policy framework and financial incentives	1) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market 2) Lack of organization of end-of-life treatment to facilitate recyclin	1)Improve resource efficiency 2)Reduce GHG emissions 3)Decoupling
Energy Efficiency Directive (EED)	Existing instrument	Direct regulation	1) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market 2) Lack of transparency	1)Improve resource efficiency 2)Reduce GHG emissions
EU Emission Trading System	Existing instrument, Re	market based instrument	1) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market	2)Reduce GHG emissions
Carbon Removals and Carbon Framing (CRCF) Regulation	Existing initiative	Direct regulation	1) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market 2) Lack of transparency and traceability, greenwashing 3) Lack of Incentives	2)Reduce GHG emissions
Carbon farming initiative	Existing initiative	market based instrument	1) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market 2) Lack of Incentives	2)Reduce GHG emissions
Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) Regulation	Existing instrument	Direct regulation	1) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market 2) Lack of transparency	1)Improve resource efficiency

“Bâtiment Biosourcé” (Bio-based Building) label (France)	Existing initiative	market based instrument, Voluntary approaches	1) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market 2) Integration of Sustainability Metrics	1)Improve resource efficiency 2)Reduce GHG emissions
RE2020 (France)	Existing instrument	Direct regulation	1) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market 2) Integration of Sustainability Metrics	1)Improve resource efficiency 2)Reduce GHG emissions
Green Public Procurement	Existing initiative, Recommended policy instrument	Direct regulation	1) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market 2) Awareness and Mindset Shift	1)Improve resource efficiency 2)Reduce GHG emissions
Limits on GHG emission per square meter in construction projects	Recommended policy instrument	Direct regulation	1) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market	1)Improve resource efficiency 2)Reduce GHG emissions
Cascading use of raw materials	Recommended policy instrument	Direct regulation	1) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market 2) ensuring bio-based material feedstock for construction materials	1)Improve resource efficiency 3)Decoupling

Construction Products Regulation (CPR)

The new Construction Products Regulation (CPR), Regulation (EU) 2024/3110, adopted in November 2024, aims to establish harmonised rules for the marketing of construction products across the European Union. This regulation responds directly to one of the main challenges identified in both case studies and stakeholder input from the IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY workshops, namely the lack of consistency and coherence in how construction products are assessed and recognised across Member States. The revised CPR provides a regulatory framework to ensure a level playing field in the European market. By establishing a unified technical language for product assessment and performance declarations, it facilitates the free movement of construction products, reduces administrative and testing costs, and strengthens market competitiveness. The regulation requires Member States to align their national provisions with this common technical language and avoid requesting non-harmonised product information, thus helping to eliminate barriers to trade. Importantly, the CPR adopts a more performance-based approach, allowing the entire life cycle of materials to be considered, including the specific environmental and functional characteristics of bio-based materials.

A major advancement under the new CPR is the integration of environmental information, particularly through Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs), into the overall product performance profile. EPDs are intended to become an essential part of how construction products are evaluated and compared. However, while some Member States already mandate EPDs, their recognition and standardisation across the EU remains inconsistent. Greater harmonisation is still needed to fully embed EPDs within the common technical language of the CPR and ensure their equal legal value throughout the single market. By addressing these gaps, the new CPR not only enhances regulatory clarity and efficiency but also opens the door for wider acceptance and implementation of low-carbon, circular, and bio-based construction materials across Europe.

Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD)

The revised Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) entered into force across all EU Member States in May 2024. It is designed to accelerate the renovation rate, with a particular focus on the worst-performing buildings in each country. The directive outlines a comprehensive set of policies and support mechanisms aimed at improving the energy performance of buildings and upgrading the existing building stock through targeted actions. A key innovation of the revised EPBD is the introduction of a Whole Life Carbon (WLC) framework, which marks a significant step

forward in recognising the full climate impact of buildings, including both operational and embodied carbon. This shift creates major opportunities for bio-based building materials, which are often lower in embodied carbon and can actively store carbon over the building's life cycle.

The directive supports several measures where bio-based materials offer distinct advantages over conventional materials. These include:

- Recognition of embodied carbon in building performance assessments
- Incentives for low-carbon construction methods and materials
- The use of material passports to support reuse and circularity
- The promotion of buildings that offer not only high energy efficiency, but also good indoor environmental quality

By addressing both operational and material-related emissions, the revised EPBD strengthens the case for integrating bio-based, circular construction solutions, contributing to the EU's broader climate and resource-efficiency goals.

Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP)

The European Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP) is a central pillar of the European Green Deal, designed to accelerate the EU's transition toward a sustainable, low-carbon, and resource-efficient economy. Within this broader framework, the construction sector plays a critical role due to its high resource consumption and waste generation. One of the key initiatives under CEAP is the Sustainable Product Policy Initiative, which promotes the creation of products that are durable, repairable, recyclable, and made from recycled or renewable materials. This approach aligns closely with the principles of circularity and opens up new opportunities for the integration of bio-based materials in building products and components. The CEAP also includes Ecodesign Requirements for Products, which aim to systematically embed sustainability into product design. For the construction industry, this means a stronger push toward innovative, low-impact materials, increasing the relevance and market potential of bio-based solutions such as wood, hemp, straw, and other natural fibres. In addition, the CEAP places strong emphasis on material recovery, particularly from demolition and renovation activities. It calls for the development of systems and infrastructure that enable higher rates of reuse, recycling, and resource recovery, helping to close material loops and reduce the environmental footprint of the built environment. Together, these measures create a supportive policy environment for the adoption of circular construction practices and the mainstreaming of bio-based materials, contributing to the broader goals of climate neutrality and resource efficiency in the EU.

EU climate law, Renovation wave, NEB and Strategy for a Sustainable Built Environment

The Renovation Wave initiative is a key component of the European Green Deal, which identifies the renovation of both public and private buildings as essential to achieving the EU's climate and energy objectives. The plan explicitly acknowledges the potential of bio-based products to reduce whole life-cycle carbon emissions in buildings. While bio-based materials are not the central focus of the Renovation Wave, they offer significant advantages in scenarios where a circular economy is the prevailing model. One of the innovative elements within the Renovation Wave is the New European Bauhaus initiative, which brings a design-led perspective to renovation. It emphasises aesthetic quality, inclusiveness, and sustainability, moving beyond purely technical improvements in building performance. A notable contribution to this initiative is Wood4Bauhaus, launched by the European wood-based sector. This platform promotes innovation and collaboration in the use of wood and other bio-based materials in construction, aligning with both design excellence and climate action.

Complementing these efforts, the EU Strategy for a Sustainable Built Environment aims to ensure coherence across multiple policy domains, including climate action, energy and resource efficiency, construction and demolition waste management, accessibility, digitalisation, and skills development. Central to this strategy is the promotion of a circular economy based on recycling, reuse, and material recovery, where carbon storage and support for a sustainable and circular bio-based industry can play a pivotal role.

Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification (CRCF) Regulation

The Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification (CRCF) Regulation is a forthcoming EU regulation designed to establish a robust, transparent, and harmonised system for certifying high-quality carbon removals across Europe. Its goal is to ensure that carbon removals—whether nature-based, material-based, or technological—are measurable, verifiable, additional, durable, and genuinely contribute to reducing atmospheric CO₂ levels. The CRCF will create EU-wide certification standards that apply across various contexts, including voluntary carbon markets, corporate sustainability reporting, public funding schemes, and eventually the EU’s climate accounting mechanisms. A key pillar of the framework is the Carbon Farming Initiative, which focuses on leveraging the carbon sequestration potential of agriculture and forestry through practices like agroforestry, soil carbon enhancement, and wetland restoration. Importantly, the CRCF also acknowledges carbon storage in long-lasting products and materials, such as wood-based construction materials and biochar. This recognition creates a vital link between carbon farming and the circular bioeconomy, allowing carbon captured on the land to be stored within industrial value chains, particularly in bio-based construction, packaging, and biomaterials.

By aligning land-based removals with climate-friendly innovation across sectors, the CRCF and Carbon Farming Initiative provide the foundation for a credible, science-based system that supports both nature-based solutions and the scaling of low-carbon technologies in the EU’s transition to climate neutrality.

“Bâtiment Biosourcé” (Bio-based Building) label & RE2020

The “Bâtiment Biosourcé” label is a French certification that recognises buildings incorporating a significant proportion of bio-based materials—resources derived from renewable biological sources such as wood, hemp, flax, straw, or cellulose. Introduced by the French government in 2012, the label was designed to promote the use of natural, low-carbon materials in the construction sector, supporting both environmental objectives and the local bioeconomy. To earn the Bâtiment Biosourcé label, a building must meet specific thresholds regarding the minimum amount of bio-based material, measured in kilograms of dry mass per square meter of floor area. These requirements vary depending on the building type and certification level (Levels 1 to 3), encouraging architects and developers to integrate materials such as cross-laminated timber, hempcrete, straw panels, and plant-fibre insulation into both structural and non-structural elements. The label reinforces broader sustainability goals by emphasising carbon storage, material circularity, and local sourcing. Notably, France is one of the few countries actively encouraging the use of bio-based materials in construction through such dedicated policy instruments.

In line with this commitment, RE2020 (Réglementation Environnementale 2020), France’s most recent environmental regulation for new buildings, came into effect in January 2022. RE2020 builds on previous energy-focused standards by introducing a more comprehensive environmental framework. It places strong emphasis on reducing greenhouse gas emissions, enhancing energy efficiency, and prioritizing low-carbon and bio-based materials. For the first time in France, the regulation mandates Life LCA of buildings, accounting for both operational emissions (from heating, cooling, and lighting) and embodied carbon (from construction materials, transport, and end-of-life processes). RE2020 also introduces carbon ceilings for new residential buildings, which

will tighten over time. These thresholds are expected to accelerate the shift toward sustainable construction practices, promoting the use of wood, straw, hempcrete, and other natural alternatives in place of carbon-intensive materials like concrete and steel.

Together, initiatives like the Bâtiment Biosourcé label and RE2020 represent significant steps toward a more circular, resource-efficient, and climate-resilient built environment. They demonstrate how regulation can effectively drive innovation and mainstream the use of bio-based solutions in the construction industry.

Limits on GHG emissions & Cascading use of raw materials

Based on case studies, stakeholder input, and discussions during the IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY workshops, some new policy instruments or initiatives were recommended that align with the goals of the European Green Deal. One key proposal is the introduction of GHG emission limits per square meter in construction projects. This measure would help position bio-based materials as more climate-friendly alternatives to conventional, fossil-based options, thereby incentivising their use.

Another important recommendation is the introduction of regulations promoting the cascading use of raw materials. This approach prioritises the use of biomass and virgin bio-based materials, such as wood, in long-life applications first, such as construction, before being reused or recycled and only used for energy recovery at the final stage. Such a system ensures that bio-based resources remain within the circular economy for as long as possible, maximizing their environmental and economic value.

3 TEXTILE SECTOR

3.1 Short description of the sector and the 3 case studies

The textile industry contributes to 10% of CO₂ emissions and 20% of wastewater worldwide (Sahimaa, 2023), ranking among the top industries for greenhouse gas emissions, water, and land use impacts (Köhler et al., 2021). The fibre production has more than doubled since 2000. The fast fashion trend leads to overconsumption, where consumers can afford to buy more and wear the garments only a few times before discarding them, leading to intense use of environmental resources (Płonka, 2023). The amount of the produced textile fibres in 2023 was 124 MT globally. At the same time, 92 million tons of textile waste were produced globally. The average per capita consumption of textiles in the world continues to increase. In the EU, it was around 15 kg per person per year and declined a bit during COVID, but it reached 19 kg per person per year since 2022 (EEA, forthcoming). The majority (67%) of the fibres used in the textile industry are synthetic (fossil-based, such as polyester). Around 26% are natural fibres (plant- and animal-based), and the rest are manmade cellulosic fibres (Textile Exchange, 2024 and CIRFS-European Man-Made fibres association, 2023 statistics). Only 1% of textile waste is recycled into fibre (fibre to fibre) (Textile Exchange, 2024). It is clear that the textiles sector has many environmental challenges to address. However, the sector organisation is still strongly linear and fossil-dominated. The need for de-fossilisation, reduction of resource use through increased circularity minimising waste and maximising resource efficiency in combination with lower consumption is urgently needed.

For the textiles sector, three case studies were selected and extensively described and analysed. All three case studies are examples that can contribute to bringing down resource use and GHG emissions in the textile industry. The results for the case studies are presented in SUSTRACK D3.3, but here the focus is on presenting the main conclusions and recommendations. The first textile case study is on the Prato value chain. Prato is a textile region (located in Tuscany) and is considered one of the largest industrial districts in Italy and the largest textile centre in Europe, handling approximately 15% of the world's recycled clothing. The second case study concerns the Lyocell value chain. Lyocell is one of the several manmade cellulosic fibres (MMCFs), also called regenerated fibres, which have entered the fibre-textile market in recent years. The last case study is about the TERNUA clothing manufacturer value chain that uses the wool of Basque and Navarre (Spain) sheep breed called Latxa for insulation material in high-quality jackets.

3.2 Main challenges and opportunities in the transition to a CBBE in the textiles sector

The challenges for the transition of the mainly linear and strong fossil-based sector towards a more circular bio-based textiles sector are described in this section. These are based on the perspectives derived from the detailed analysis of the three case studies and the different insights obtained during the SUSTRACK DESIGN and IMPLEMENT workshops with stakeholders both specific to the case studies and the wider EU textiles sector.

The challenges can be categorised according to market, sustainability and policy aspects.

Market dimension challenges

One of the main challenges faced is that currently the costs of bio-based fibres, e.g., MMCFs, or recycled fibres derived from discarded textiles are too expensive to compete with other mostly fossil and cotton-based fibres. Most of these fossil-based textiles that are entering the EU market from all over the world, but especially China, are very low in price. Even recycled materials are

often more expensive than the virgin synthetic or cotton ones. In addition, overconsumption and overproduction in the clothing market, especially stimulated by fast fashion and low prices of mostly synthetic textiles, make it very difficult to enter the market with higher costs of textile products based on MMCFs or recycled, discarded textiles. The higher additional cost for recycling and generation of MMCFs is simply not rewarded in the highly competitive, globally organised clothing markets. This is a very pertinent challenge. Firstly, because negative externality costs are not (yet) reflected in textile products. Secondly, because consumer behaviour on the textile and fashion markets is still most strongly driven by lower prices. From a consumer perspective, business models have created a culture based on volume-driven consumption, which has become deeply embedded in societal norms. Our society thrives on rapid change, fast consumption, and immediate pleasure, promoting a cycle of consumption that extends beyond textiles to many other sectors. This fast fashion culture, along with constant social comparisons, has shaped consumer behaviour and decision-making, driving unsustainable practices.

In the case of Prato, it was demonstrated that production costs for recycled wool remain 10-20% higher than virgin wool, primarily driven by technological and operational limitations. Despite these challenges, market penetration is steadily increasing, with recycled wool products now capturing 15% of Prato's market share. However, smaller companies continue to face significant financial barriers, which limit their ability to compete effectively. In 2023, for example, Prato's manufacturing production showed a downward trend -7.8%, compared to an 8.7% increase in 2022 and in 2024, this downward trend continued. The flood damage suffered by the Prato textile industry did not help, but other more fundamental factors played a role, such as lack of confidence in the markets they operate in, high cost of energy and transportation, rising raw material costs, and intensified competition from low-cost brands.

Also, for the MMCFs, such as Lyocell, it was confirmed that competition with incumbent fossil and cotton-based production systems is difficult. This is related to higher production costs, and as long as the market is not (sufficiently) rewarding for the lower environmental impacts in the production of MMCFs, strong market penetration remains difficult. The other aspect why the market entry of new recycled and MMCFs is challenging is because new fibres have new properties, to which existing standardised production chains need to be adapted. For each fibre with a changed fibre property, the textile chain needs to collect knowledge on how to industrially treat the products in the whole processing chain from fibre to garment. This requires investments and takes time.

In addition, for the Latxa sheep wool in the Basque Country in Spain, the entrance into the market has been challenging. This is because the Latxa wool is not as fine or soft as that of most other sheep breeds specifically bred for wool production. Because of this, the wool produced by these Latxa sheep was discarded or incinerated directly without providing any additional income to farmers for a long time. By providing a market for Latxa wool, initiatives like the ARTILE jacket project brought a new business model back. It ensured that farmers are compensated for their wool, thereby enhancing their economic sustainability. This financial incentive encourages farmers to maintain and invest in their Latxa sheep flocks, thus promoting the conservation of indigenous sheep breeds in the Basque Country.

Sustainability dimension challenges

Currently, the transparency and traceability for textile products are largely lacking, especially where it relates to sustainability. This is difficult to address because the textiles sector is very globalised and competitive. Furthermore, there is a wide lack of education and awareness among consumers about the circular and/or bio-based materials used and how they differ from the standard synthetic and cotton materials most commonly used. This makes it difficult to stimulate more sustainable production and consumption practices, but is also a reason why higher transparency and traceability of textile products are needed. The transparency and traceability of the sustainability of the fibres and textiles produced in the three case studies are therefore receiving a lot of attention. This is also why, in the Lyocell MMCF case, concern is expressed about ensuring the sustainable sourcing of the production chain. It is specifically mentioned that the sustainable sourcing of MMCFs is a challenge, which makes the certification of the final MMCF products more complicated. Lack of certified resources also makes the constant availability of sustainable feedstocks to scale up the process complicated. In the case of the Ternua Latxa wool, sustainability is a core concern requiring a lot of attention. This is because wool washing is a difficult step and requires much water and chemicals. Improving the sustainability of this process requires investments in knowledge and advanced installations, and this is even more challenging for the continuation of existing and new decentralised washing installations for wool, such as is the case in the Ternua.

The problems with sustainability in the incumbent mostly fossil and cotton-based linear production systems, are clear. Still, also for the alternative, more circular and bio-based systems of which the three case studies are examples, there are still many research and innovation gaps in relation to sustainable practices in the whole textile supply chain. Moreover, the need for setting up wider collaborations between textile manufacturers, waste management companies, biomass producers and providers and local and national government organisations is a challenge. In all three cases, the role of SMEs should be strengthened. In the Prato case, for example, it was mentioned that the small companies, constituting a significant part of Prato's textile ecosystem, often encounter difficulties securing funding and incorporating technologies due to financial and technical constraints. Inconsistent enforcement of waste segregation laws and the absence of standardised sustainability reporting frameworks further hinder the uniform implementation of circular practices across stakeholders. In addition, in relation to energy efficiency, challenges are encountered. In all case studies, there are regional and national policies that support the transition to more efficiency and the use of renewable energy sources. However, high upfront costs continue to act as a barrier to widespread adoption. Targeted subsidies and financial incentives could accelerate the integration of renewable energy across the district and are certainly needed.

Another challenge is the lack of data, methodologies and adequate monitoring and evaluation frameworks, which hinders transitions to more sustainable practices in the textiles sector. This was, for example, illustrated in the Prato and Ternua cases specifically. On the one hand, the circular bio-based system in Prato shows clear environmental, economic, and social benefits compared to the fossil-based system, notably in reducing resource use and enhancing community well-being. However, challenges such as high costs and limited inclusivity persist. Research gaps include inconsistent methodologies for measuring water use and renewable energy adoption, as

well as data collection challenges for SMEs. Social impacts on marginalised groups also require further exploration. Furthermore, fragmented and incomplete data hinder the ability to assess the long-term environmental impacts of measures to improve sustainability in the sectors.

In the Ternua case, specific data and methodology limitations were reported, which hamper realistic reporting of resource use and availability and make reporting on social indicators difficult. It was observed in the Ternua case, but also in more general terms, that many environmental indicators are supported by established international standards, but transparency remains deficient for certain metrics, such as the proportion of materials derived from specific renewable resources, such as animal by-products. Social indicators, particularly those concerning inclusivity and resilience, encounter even greater obstacles due to inconsistent data availability at regional levels and divergent methodological approaches, limiting comparability and scalability. Resources such as the Social Hotspots Database offer valuable data for assessing social impacts but lack comprehensive coverage and regional levels. The absence of standardised data collection frameworks further exacerbates these challenges, particularly in regions with underdeveloped infrastructures or in small enterprises globally. This highlights the critical need for unified methodologies to ensure effective evaluation and meaningful progress in sustainability.

Policy dimension challenges

Overall, it becomes clear both from the case studies and the DESIGN and IMPLEMENT workshops that more policy guidance on sustainability claims is needed and that in general the existing policy frameworks facilitate more the continuation of existing unsustainable practices in the textile sector (and the economy in general) while introduction of more sustainable circular and bio-based practices are insufficiently supported. One mechanism mentioned was that the current governance structure tends to tax labour more than goods and does not address environmental externality costs. In the current system, no stimulation is given to recyclability, lowering footprints and prevention of microplastics losses to the environment, and it does not prevent green washing, unfounded circularity and sustainability claims. One related aspect in this regard is that sufficiently clear and inclusive definitions for bio-based plastics, biopolymers and bio-based fibres make certification and labelling more challenging, and this is another policy gap.

In the Prato case, for example, it is mentioned that at the regional and local level, good progress is being made in improving the policy framework to support more sustainable production chains. For example, the EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles and Legislative Decree 116/2020 encourage resource recovery and waste management, while the Made in Italy Law (Law 206/2023) and local initiatives such as Next Generation Prato focus on strengthening the value chain and fostering innovation. Certification schemes, such as the Cardato Recycled Certification, further incentivise transparency and sustainability, positioning Prato as a leader in recycled textiles. However, enforcement inconsistencies and the absence of standardised reporting frameworks across regions expose critical policy gaps that impede uniform implementation. The aspect of the lack of standardised regional policies and fragmented enforcement mechanisms was also mentioned in the Ternua case, undermining progress. This is because inconsistent regulations create barriers to the uniform adoption of circular economy practices.

In all case studies, there was also mention of crucial stakeholders such as manufacturers and retailers, but also financial institutions and supranational and international policymakers,

exhibiting limited interest and even resistance to bringing the transition to more circularity in the textiles sector. This is creating bottlenecks in resource allocation and broader improvements in the systemic adoption. The stakeholders' reluctance may stem from perceived economic risks or the higher costs associated with adopting sustainable practices. Similarly, the lack of standardised regional policies or fragmented enforcement mechanisms undermines progress, as inconsistent regulations create barriers to uniform adoption of circular economy practices.

3.3 Recommendations and good practice examples

Overall, the three case studies could be seen as good practice examples of production systems that contribute to the transition to a more sustainable textile sector. From the case study analysis and the SUSTRACK DESIGN and IMPLEMENT workshops, many more specific recommendations and good practice examples were obtained to address the different barriers discussed in the former.

The case studies are examples of good practices:

The **Prato case study** is a good example in itself because it illustrates how a traditional textile-based industrial region transitions into a circular bio-based economic centre. This transition process was brought about through the introduction of a robust policy framework in which European, national, and local policies were integrated to form the foundation for sustainable practices and through the introduction of certification schemes, such as the “Cardato Recycled” for recycled wool. The policies introduced were the EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles and Legislative Decree 116/2020, which encourage resource recovery and waste management, while the Made in Italy Law (Law 206/2023) and local initiatives such as Next Generation Prato focus on strengthening the value chain and fostering innovation. Still, it can be recommended specifically for Prato's sustainability performance to enhance the enforcement of policies like waste segregation under Legislative Decree 116/2020 and implement standardised reporting frameworks that can ensure consistent progress across all stakeholders. The specific “Cardato Recycled” certification was set up by the Prato Chamber of Commerce for carded wool in collaboration with a consortium of different local organisations and producers' federations. The certification is controlled and validated by the Société Générale de Surveillance (SGS) and to be recognised as such, labels, fabrics and yarns must: (i) be produced locally, (ii) be made with at least 65% recycled material, (iii) have measured the environmental impact of the entire production cycle, taking into account three aspects, i.e., the impacts of water consumption, energy consumption and CO₂ emissions.

The **Lyocell MMCF case** is a good example of practice, in that it can contribute well to making the textiles sector more environmentally sustainable because the involved conversion processes of cellulose to fibres have a very low environmental impact and high quality. Lyocell is a good example of an MMCF that now forms an interesting alternative to the fossil and cotton-based fibres, which make up the majority of the fibres used in textiles worldwide, and which have a considerably higher negative impact on the environment in terms of GHG emissions, water consumption, and wider pollution. What is also attractive is that MMCFs are produced from bio-based sources and are hence 100% biodegradable. Therefore, their increased use in textile applications can also help the reduction in microplastic pollution from fossil textile sources. What is also sustainable for MMCFs like lyocell is that they can be produced from both biomass and waste due to the high vegetal fibre share of the textile waste. Using textile waste as a resource

is attractive from a circularity perspective, but technically still very challenging, and that is why MMCF are still produced from primary biomass sources by 99%, only for 1% from waste sources. To ensure the production of MMCFs can continue to grow, to replace the unsustainable fossil and cotton textile products, several recommendations can be made. Firstly, more financial and R&D support is needed to stimulate technology developments that extract the cellulose fibres from the mostly mixed fossil-non-fossil textile waste streams produced in the current society. Secondly, end-of-life treatment of textile wastes can be more strictly regulated to also improve access to textile waste sources to produce new MMCF fibres from. Thirdly, it is recommended to accelerate the introduction of ecodesign criteria which force producers of textile products on EU markets to be recyclable and environmentally friendly. This will increase the amount of textiles that can be recycled in fibre-to-fibre MMCF production processes, but it will also help to significantly increase the market share of sustainable MMCF fibres like lyocell at the expense of unsustainable fossil and cotton-based fibres.

The **Ternua Latxa sheep wool case** is a good example of valorisation of a biological resource, which used to be discarded and burned before, and that is coupled with the revitalisation of a traditional sector of indigenous sheep breeds that now provides a better and more secure income to farmers. The use of sheep wool as an insulation material is a good example of how bio-based materials are used, also contributing to the defossilisation of the textile sector. Since there are many EU regional examples of lower quality wool (and other bio-resources) having no economic outlet, EU and national strategies are needed to address such a market failure. Therefore, it is recommended to rethink industrial processes by establishing at the EU and national level a strategic industrialisation program to leverage its historical knowledge and expertise in wool processing. This initiative could help create a competitive hub for wool production by fostering innovation and improving the industry's efficiency and profitability, and simultaneously contribute to the stimulation of rural economies. The most critical issue in the wool sector is the lack of facilities for washing and processing wool, compounded by technical and pollution-related challenges. To address this, aid policies for industrial washing facilities and technological advancements should be developed, along with support for existing facilities. This may also involve action of local governments to facilitate the process of getting permits.

Recommendations from the case studies:

Overarching recommendations to improve sustainable practices in the textile sector are summarised along the following lines.

- Improved market penetration also needs to be addressed through a policy response to address the cost disparities. Financial policy instruments that can be recommended in this regard were reduced VAT for recycled products and sustainable bio-based alternatives to fossil-based conventional textiles, and penalties for unsustainable non-renewable and virgin resources use. Also, Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) measures and digital product passports were suggested quite widely, and this is in line with policy measures the EU is already working on. For example, the EPR fees for unsustainable fibres may encourage more sustainable production and consumption. Labelling and certification in combination with policy instruments (e.g., legislation) may ensure the sustainability claims in EU are credible.

- As to certification, the focus should be more on processes producing recycled fibres and other renewable MMCFs. This also requires simultaneously setting up collaboration and policy structures that ensure the sustainability claims in the EU are credible. More improvements are also possible in the traceability and monitoring through labelling and certification of textiles, covering the whole production chain from feedstock sourcing to end-of-life treatments. An EU instrument that is already announced to be developed for this purpose is the digital product passport (DPP). This will need to ensure uniformity in green labelling but also fill data gaps on issues like carbon footprints, (sustainable) energy use, water input and pollution prevention, land use, and use of fair and socially sustainable production approaches.
- Still more effort is needed to develop data collection frameworks and establish standardised tools and methodologies to measure and report sustainability metrics consistently, ensuring reliable comparability across systems and stakeholders. From the case studies it became clear that there are still limitations in data, methodologies and challenges with comparison of sustainability performance of different textile products.
- Enhance financial support by introducing targeted subsidies, grants and loans to help companies, including SMEs, to adopt advanced sustainability practices, enabling them to compete effectively in the market. Providing tailored funding mechanisms and technical assistance programs for SMEs will empower marginalised stakeholders to participate fully in the transition. Moreover, developing formal mechanisms to include rural communities in decision-making processes will foster greater inclusivity and resilience.
- Invest in R&D for technological advancements and wider scientific insights to support transitions to a more circular and sustainable textile sector at different geographic scales, from global to local. Furthermore, these initiatives must be accompanied by investments in research to address gaps in areas such as biodiversity restoration, water recycling systems, and renewable energy adoption.
- Create programs for education and information sharing in relation to (un)sustainable consumer and production practices in textiles. This will help fostering consumer demand and industry-wide alignment with circular principles and provide explanations about the benefits of recycled textiles. For instance, expanding climate change education programs and leveraging NGOs to promote recycling and sustainable consumption practices can further engage citizens and create a culture of sustainability.
- Finally, there is a continued need to further fostering collaboration between industry, academia, and civil society to co-create solutions for systemic challenges, thus leveraging diverse expertise and perspectives.

3.4 Policy recommendations to stimulate transition and enhance resource efficiency

In the former sections, several recommendations were already made in relation to policy measures that can be taken to stimulate the transition to a more circular and sustainable textiles sector in the EU. In this section, we present in greater detail the policy instruments already identified in the case studies as good practice examples, followed by a discussion of policy instruments that can be implemented in the near future and for which potentially details are already being worked out by the EU and national governments. This section also links to the work done in WP5 of SUSTRACK, where policies have been extensively reviewed and detailed policy recommendations

are produced, taking account of extensive reviews of literature, several exchanges with stakeholders in the DEPLOY workshops and through a survey consultation.

An overview of the good policy examples and the recommended new policy instruments is presented in Table 3. The policy instruments are linked to the challenges for the transition they address and that were discussed in the former section, and also to the CBBE targets they contribute to (see Appendix 2).

Table 3 Overview of policy instruments identified to tackle barriers and/or stimulate transition or both

Policy instrument	Existing Good example instrument or proposed or recommended policy instrument?	Type of instrument (direct regulation, market based instrument, or other) (see Appendix 1)	Challenge addressed	Contribution to CBBE target (see Appendix 2)
EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles	Existing good example instrument	Information and advice sharing system	1)Lack of transparency and traceability, greenwashing 2) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market 3)Technical challenges to recycle textiles 4)Lack of consumer awareness	1)Improve resource efficiency 2)Reduce GHG emissions 3)Decoupling
Ecodesign criteria Sets mandatory requirements for product design, material composition, and end-of-life management e.g., products that are put in the market are more durable, recyclable, and environmentally friendly.	Proposed policy instrument (Announced in EU Strategy for sustainable and circular textiles)	Direct regulation but can also be Information sharing system or Market based signaling approach. Depends on how it is implemented	1)Lack of transparency and traceability, greenwashing 2) Lack of organization of end-of-life treatment to facilitate recycling 3)Technical challenges to recycle textiles	1)Resource use efficiency
Reduced/green VAT for recycled and sustainable bio-based textiles and repair services	Recommended policy instrument	Market-based instrument	1) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market	1)Improve resource efficiency 2)Reduce GHG emissions
Higher VAT or carbon tax on unsustainable textile items, e.g. fast fashion, fossil-based textiles, textiles based on unsustainable virgin resources	Recommended policy instrument	Market-based instrument	1) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market	1)Improve resource efficiency 2)Reduce GHG emissions
Extended Producer Responsibility Producers are responsible for their products that are put in the market to be circular and to collect them at the end of the life.	Proposed policy instrument	Direct regulation	1) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market 2) Lack of organization of end-of-life treatment to facilitate recycling	1)Improve resource efficiency 2)Decoupling
Digital Product Passport	Proposed policy instrument	Direct regulation but can also be Information sharing system or Market based signaling approach. Depends on how it is implemented	1)Lack of transparency and traceability, greenwashing 2) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market	1)Improve resource efficiency 2)Reduce GHG emissions 3)Decoupling
Quota -for use of recycled (and bio-based	Recommended policy instrument	Could become direct regulation, but could also be	1) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market	1)Improve resource efficiency

) material in textiles production and imports		linked to public procurement.		2)Reduce GHG emissions
Certification, e.g “Cardato Recycled”	Good example practice	Market based signaling	1)Lack of transparency and traceability, greenwashing 2) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market	1)Improve resource efficiency 2)Reduce GHG emissions
Textile waste segregation obligation (e.g. Italian Legislative Decree 116/2020,)	Good example practice in Italy, now also implemented at EU level	Direct regulation	1)Lack of organization of end-of-life treatment to facilitate recycling	1)Resource use efficiency
Italian Special Fund for Green and Digital Transition in Fashion" Allocates €15 million to the promote investments in green and digital transition.	Good example practice in Italy	Economic instrument (subsidy)	1)Lack of transparency and traceability, greenwashing	1)Improve resource efficiency 2)Reduce GHG emissions
French anti-waste Law for a Circular Economy . Requires that unsold non-food products can no longer be destroyed	Good example practice in France. At EU level a similar law is in preparation	Direct regulation	1)Fast fashion and over-production in textile sector 2)Lack of consumer awareness	1)Improve resource efficiency 2)Reduce GHG emissions
Green Transition Directive . It empowers consumers to receive better and more harmonised information on its durability and reparability	Good example EU policy instrument since 2024. Now needs to be transposed to national laws.	Direct regulation	1)Lack of transparency and traceability, greenwashing	1)Improve resource efficiency 2) Decoupling
The Textile Labelling Regulation (EU) 1007/2011 The EU has aligned laws in all EU countries on fibre names and related labelling and marking of the fibre composition of textile products	Good example EU policy instrument	Direct regulation	1)Lack of transparency and traceability, greenwashing	1)Improve resource efficiency
The EU Ecolabel for textile products It establishes the ecological criteria for textile products	Good example EU policy instrument	Voluntary instrument	1)Lack of transparency and traceability, greenwashing	1)Improve resource efficiency
The Strategic Plan for Recovery, Transformation and Resilience in the Circular Economy (PERTE EC) Addressing ecodesigning of new garments that entail lower environmental impact, improving waste treatment by promoting reuse and recycling	Good example policy instrument in Spain specifically targeting Textiles sector.	Economic instrument (subsidy)	1) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market 2) Lack of organization of end-of-life treatment to facilitate recycling	1)Improve resource efficiency 2)Decoupling

From the case study descriptions and also the IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY workshop stakeholder discussions, it can be concluded that certain new policy instruments are quite widely recommended, and these largely overlap with the policies announced already in the *EU Strategy for sustainable and circular textiles*, adopted in March 2022. These include policy instruments, among others, the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), Extended producer responsibility (EPR) and Digital Product Passports.

The ESPR entered into force in July 2024 and applies in principle to almost all categories of physical products. It establishes a framework for setting ecodesign requirements on specific product groups. Textile products are expected to become one of these product groups, but so far, this has only been announced and not adopted in concrete rules. These rules are, however, expected to become more concrete in 2025. The ESPR aims on the one hand to introduce mandatory durability, repairability and recyclability criteria for products including textiles. On the other hand, it also announces the introduction of a Digital Product Passport (DPP), a digital identity card for products, components, and materials, which will store relevant information to support products' sustainability, promote their circularity and strengthen legal compliance. From the case studies, it has become clear that expectations are high that these types of instruments will indeed support the recycling and MMCFs sector strongly.

Additionally, modulating EPR fees and establishing standards to reduce the production costs of bio-based fibres will support sustainable business models. With the ecodesign criteria, it is also recommended to create collaboration structures for certification and labelling, ensuring that sustainability claims are standardised and credible. Additionally, in relation to the repairability principle, it was suggested to certify products as repairable, ensuring durability in design. In the discussions with stakeholders during the DEPLOY workshop, the instrument of ecodesign was generally seen as the way forward to bring fibre-to-fibre recycling further and improve resource efficiency in the textiles sector. On the other hand, weaknesses were also mentioned, and these relate to the challenge of making workable definitions for 'durability', control and monitoring of the system, which comes with high cost and administration pressure, and there were also doubts about whether textiles/garment production can be standardised at all. Recommendations made for the introduction of this ecodesign instrument were to provide proper guidelines on limiting the blending of different types of fibres to make recyclability easier. Also, the handling of textile waste should be improved to facilitate monitoring textile waste over EU borders. The scattered and dispersed availability of textile wastes makes the organisation of the recycling chain challenging, particularly because for recycling, large amounts of well-sorted textile wastes are needed. Finally, it was recommended to also extend the responsibility to the consumer, and not only to the producer.

Sustainability challenges in the textile sector also include a lack of transparency and traceability, and a lack of guidance on sustainability claims, such as recyclability and the environmental footprint of products. A critical tool to address this, which was widely recommended in the case studies and the DEPLOY workshops, is the DPP. When introduced, it is expected that DPP can provide wide access to information on the overall sustainability of products, such as carbon footprints, material origins and recyclability. This tool should be introduced along with robust network of consistent certification systems to be developed by and used for companies and public authorities.

A ban on the Destruction of Unsold Goods is another instrument that, with the entering into force of the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation, is being worked out by the EC. How it will influence the textile products is not clear yet. In France, this instrument is already in place and also applies to unsold textile garments. This AGECE law (Loi Anti-Gaspillage pour une Économie Circulaire), dictates since January 2022, and manufacturers, including in fashion, can no longer dispose of unsold goods. The French government was the first in the world to take such a measure, and more EU countries are already considering it. Also, in the case studies and the DEPLOY

workshops, it is generally seen as a measure that will indeed lead to the lowering of unsold textiles and that may reduce resource use. According to EEA (2024), the research literature states that 21% of textile products produced remain unsold and that around one-fifth of this ends up being destroyed. From a resource efficiency and GHG emission perspective, it would indeed be advisable to ban the destruction of unsold goods. During the DEPLOY workshop, some weaknesses of this measure were also mentioned. One is that it could have a leakage effect, where the unsold textiles are moved outside the EU. Another leakage effect could be that textile waste recycling will focus on the unsold textiles rather than on the real textile waste. Finally, it was also recommended that this instrument needs to be accompanied by an instrument that also discourages consumption at the source.

On the market side, several challenges need to be addressed for promoting sustainable business models. One challenge is the higher cost of recycled fibres, MMCFs, and garment repairs, which makes these models less competitive. Temporary green VAT measures, such as reducing VAT to e.g. 10% for sustainable products, can further incentivise these practices. An additional positive outcome of this approach could be that it will also attract more innovative end-of-life technologies to the EU, a challenge would be the scaling of these technologies, though.

Besides the reward of a Green VAT, an instrument that punishes unsustainable products could also be considered in the form of a carbon tax on the use of (blended or single) fossil-based textiles and/or fast fashion. Several arguments were given as to why it can be effective. The first is that this instrument has already proved to be effective in the energy markets. Secondly, it can be organised by adding products to the existing EU ETS policy, but it would also require accompanying measures through the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM). Thirdly, it is expected that initially it will face lots of resistance, but will be effective in the end in stimulating behavioural change. The weaknesses of this instrument were also identified. Firstly, there is a risk that many textile producers will move their production outside the EU. Secondly, it may lead to higher consumer prices, and this may make textiles less affordable for certain low-income groups. From a 'just' perspective, this may be undesired. Thirdly, it was recommended to design the instrument in such a way that not only the producers but also the fashion brands take responsibility for putting more sustainable products on the market.

If a tax on fast fashion is considered, it may work out positively for the more 'responsible fashion brands', but the question is very much how to exactly define what 'fast fashion' is. Furthermore, any regulation to address fast fashion will easily be seen as an intrusion into personal freedom, and this will then work out counterproductive. It should be accepted that change will require time and is not easy. At the same time, consumer awareness should be raised about sustainable and unsustainable products, and this should also be addressed through education and transparency and information sharing.

Another market-based approach to support more sustainable textile products to enter the market could be through the introduction of quotas and also public procurement for recycled and sustainable plant and animal-based fibres in textiles. Examples of this are already in place in certain countries and can work out effectively in increasing the market share of circular and sustainable products. There is, however, a recommendation that it can only work well if enough sustainable alternatives have also entered the market. Therefore, the stimulation of the market growth of recycled and bio-based textile products should be organised simultaneously. It also

implies that the development of uniform, generally accepted, and transparent sustainability criteria is urgently needed. In setting up this complex system of sustainability criteria, procurement and quotas, enough attention should also be given to burden sharing through the whole and complex value chain. For example, stricter requirements, quotas or carbon taxes can be placed at the beginning or the end of the chain. One approach could be that the recycling of fibres is subsidised through the revenues obtained from the fee on sold products.

Finally, there are still some additional candidate policy instruments that need to be mentioned that target a more end-of-life treatment of textiles. These are the introduction of recycling quota, take-back systems for textile garments in shops, tax credits or low green VAT for repair services and a deposit or refund system for textile products.

4 CHEMICAL SECTOR

4.1 Short description of the sector and the 2 case studies

The chemical sector is one of the largest and most energy-intensive industries in the EU, accounting for approximately 22% of the total final energy consumption in industry in the EU in 2020 (EEA, 2023). It is heavily reliant on fossil feedstocks for both energy and raw materials (IEA, 2022) and contributes 3.2% of total GHG emissions in the EU (EEA, 2023). In 2023, the EU chemical industry generated €655 billion in sales and employed 3.4 million people, playing a central role in the EU economy (CEFIC, 2024). However, its linear and fossil-dependent model contributes to resource depletion, pollution, and waste generation, with hazardous substances posing risks to human health and ecosystems (EEA, 2023). About 80% chemicals produced are hazardous to human health, and 28% are classified as a very toxic health hazard (Eurostat, 2024). Currently, over 98% of the carbon feedstock used in the chemical industry is fossil-based, indicating a substantial dependency on non-renewable resources and highlighting the urgent need for a transition toward more sustainable and circular alternatives (Systemiq, 2022). The European chemical sector is thus under increasing pressure to decarbonise, reduce toxicity, and transition to safer and more sustainable alternatives. Circular economy strategies—such as renewable carbon sourcing, improved recycling technologies, and demand-side innovation—are critical to achieving climate neutrality and reducing the sector’s environmental and health burdens (European Commission, 2020; European Commission, 2023). The transformation of the EU chemical sector will require systemic changes, including policy coherence, investments in green technologies, and stronger value-chain collaboration to foster circularity, minimise waste, and shift away from fossil-based production systems. In addition to these environmental and health concerns, there are structural, economic and regulatory barriers that hinder the adoption and uptake of bio-based alternatives, which will be elaborated on in this chapter.

For the chemicals sector, two case studies were selected and extensively described and analysed. Both case studies are examples that can contribute to a reduction of resource use and GHG emissions. While the results for the case studies are presented in SUSTRACK D3.3, the current study focuses on presenting the main conclusions and recommendations.

The first case study features Monoethylene Glycol (MEG), an organic compound and a drop-in chemical, chemically identical to fossil-based MEG (i.e., $C_2H_6O_2$). Traditionally, MEG has been produced from fossil-based feedstocks such as ethane, propane, or naphtha through a multi-step petrochemical process that transforms hydrocarbon feedstocks into a versatile chemical used across several industries (Ullmann's Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemistry, 2011). MEG produced from agricultural residues and lignocellulose-rich raw materials, mostly known as bio-MEG, offers the possibility of a reduction in CO_2 emissions and decreased dependency on fossil resources. (Bio-)MEG is used in diverse fields of application, such as the production of polyester fibres and polyethylene terephthalate (PET) resins, as well as antifreeze in coolant agents. It is used significantly in end-use sectors such as textiles and packaging, while also being a component for the production of adhesives, sealants, paints and coatings, and other chemicals.

The second case study concerns the conversion of (non-recyclable, non-compostable) municipal solid waste (MSW) into methanol (i.e., bio-methanol). Bio-methanol is a drop-in chemical, chemically identical to fossil-based methanol (i.e., CHO_3H). Currently, nearly all methanol is produced from synthesis gas (i.e., syngas). Bio-based syngas can be produced through the gasification of various biomass sources, such as lignocellulosic crops, wood, forestry and agricultural residues, as well as municipal solid waste (MSW). However, currently about 80% of the methanol production is based on natural gas, 17% on coal, with only 3% based on other (biogenic) feedstocks. Despite its promising contribution to more sustainable fuels, especially in

hard-to-abate sectors (e.g., shipping), the role bio-methanol could play in non-energy applications remains underexposed. Hence, this case study seeks to shed light on bio-methanol as a highly versatile chemical building block, which like its fossil counterpart can be used to produce hundreds of everyday products, such as textiles, adhesives, paints, pharmaceuticals, and car parts.

4.2 Main challenges and opportunities in the transition to a CBBE in the chemical sector

Several challenges are faced in the transition of the chemical sector towards a CBBE. Key to it is the lack of regulatory support addressing both GHG emissions and toxicity. While efforts to reduce emissions through material recycling are gaining attention, they carry the risk of reintroducing or concentrating hazardous substances in subsequent products. Furthermore, current chemical regulations tend to focus on a limited set of substances deemed to be of very high concern, leaving a large number of potentially harmful chemicals insufficiently addressed.

Beyond these overarching concerns, the transition toward bio-based chemical production is hindered by challenges across multiple dimensions, particularly in the **market**, **policy**, and **sustainability** dimensions.

Market dimension challenges

From a market perspective, the development of bio-based chemicals is constrained by several interlinked barriers. One of the main obstacles is the **limited access to financing for early-stage technologies**. Many bio-based chemical innovations are not yet mature and often require substantial capital expenditure (CAPEX) to establish first-of-a-kind production facilities. The absence of established supply chains for bio-based materials further amplifies investment risks, placing a significant burden on first movers. Whereas investors prefer settling on long-term off-take agreements to secure supply, companies tend to favour flexibility, especially in fast-changing market segments such as bio-based chemicals. In the bio-methanol case, it was observed that a large industrial player considered moving its business to the USA, due to its more favourable investment climate.

Although public funding mechanisms exist in some cases, these typically cover only a portion of CAPEX and rarely extend to operational expenditures (OPEX). The OPEX requirements are, in turn, subject to volatility depending on factors such as feedstock availability and market demand, introducing further uncertainty for potential investors.

In addition to financial risks, the **cost-competitiveness of bio-based chemicals** remains a major concern. While fossil-based chemicals benefit from decades of process optimisation and scale, bio-based alternatives are often still in developmental stages, resulting in higher production costs. The costs for producing bio-methanol, for instance, are substantially higher than those associated with the production of fossil methanol. Consequently, the success of bio-methanol hinges on the willingness of methanol-relying companies to pay a price premium, which limits the economic incentive for the utilisation of waste. For example, in the bio-methanol case, another non-level playing field exists between its energetic versus non-energetic uses. Since the extension of the EU Emission Trading Scheme (ETS) to, among others, the shipping sector, the expected demand for maritime fuels with a low fossil carbon footprint has risen significantly. The economic advantages of applying bio-methanol as a fuel could hamper its uptake in non-energetic, chemical applications.

The market is also challenged by the **difficulty of integrating previously disconnected sectors**, such as agriculture and high-value chemical manufacturing, due to the emerging nature of bio-based products. Moreover, the availability and price of biomass feedstocks are subject to fluctuations, especially given the growing competition from other sectors, including food, feed, and bioenergy. These pressures are expected to intensify toward 2050, potentially threatening feedstock security for the chemical industry.

Policy dimension challenges

From the policy perspective, one of the most pressing issues is the **absence of dedicated regulatory support for bio-based chemical products**. Unlike bioenergy, which benefits from clear legislative frameworks such as the Renewable Energy Directive (RED), bio-based chemicals lack similar recognition and incentives. This policy gap creates an uneven playing field, often making it more attractive to use bio-based feedstocks for energy applications (e.g., ethanol or methanol) rather than for higher-value chemical production. This not only hinders the further valorisation of these molecules but also limits their substitution potential for petrochemical-based products.

A further complication lies in the general **instability and lack of harmonisation in policymaking**, which undermines investor confidence and obstructs the market expansion of established bio-based chemicals. In the bio-methanol case, for example, it was found that a single, broadly supported political vision on the utilisation of waste does not exist. In the Netherlands, a recurring dilemma is whether the gasification of waste can be considered an improvement in comparison with the dominant MSW treatment method: incineration coupled to energy recovery. Similarly, at the European level, gasification is mistakenly tied to energy recovery in the waste processing hierarchy, which has readily obstructed licensing procedures for industrial bio-methanol plants.

While **decarbonization remains the primary focus of existing policy measures**, a shift toward *defossilisation* is more appropriate for the chemical sector. Since chemicals inherently rely on carbon-based building blocks, the goal should not be to eliminate carbon per se, but rather to replace fossil-derived carbon with renewable sources. This, in turn, calls for more robust systems of carbon tracking and accounting across complex, global value chains—a challenge that requires deep collaboration among multiple actors and jurisdictions.

Sustainability dimension challenges

In terms of sustainability, a critical inconsistency persists between the expectations placed on bio-based products and those applied to conventional petrochemicals. Bio-based chemicals are often required to demonstrate their sustainability credentials, despite the fact that no equivalent requirements exist for fossil-based counterparts. This creates a regulatory asymmetry that can disincentivise innovation in sustainable alternatives. While sustainability criteria are well established for bioenergy and biofuels under the RED framework, no analogous set of EU-level criteria exists for bio-based chemicals.

Moreover, the **ability to conduct robust sustainability assessments is hampered by a lack of data and methodological standardisation**. Environmental performance is the most frequently evaluated aspect, but there is limited capacity to adequately assess the economic and social dimensions due to data scarcity. The **absence of a harmonised LCA methodology** for bio-based products further complicates efforts to benchmark and improve their sustainability performance. In particular, inconsistencies in how biogenic carbon is accounted for, especially in cradle-to-gate versus cradle-to-grave assessments, create confusion and reduce the utility of LCA as a decision-making tool. Likewise, the presence of **toxic substances and hazardous materials in chemical products** represents a significant barrier to achieving circularity within the sector. Hazardous

additives and substances of concern often inhibit reuse, recycling, and recovery processes due to accumulation or formation of Non-intentionally added substances (NIAS) in the material streams, limiting the quality of recyclates, and increasing the complexity and costs associated with decontamination.

In the bio-methanol case, another challenge was found in **the unequal allocation of sustainability benefits from waste valorisation**. For example, if a municipality diverts its MSW away from incineration to methanol production, an emission saving is achieved at the municipal level. However, the chemical producers may have more difficulty processing the waste, causing higher emissions at the plant level. In this example, the benefits of one party are at the expense of the other, *trade-off*. Even though a net emission saving is reached, typically only one actor reaps the benefits (also to avoid double-counting), which can, in practice, inhibit all actors from taking action to avoid risks of loss-making.

4.3 Recommendations and good practice examples

The case studies are examples of good practices:

The **bio-MEG** case study, which considers the production of MEG from forest and agricultural biomass, illustrates a good example of the transition towards a CBBE. It presents a chemically identical substitute for fossil-based MEG and is produced using renewable feedstocks, primarily agricultural and forestry residues, thereby reducing greenhouse gas emissions and fossil resource dependence. The value chain leverages advanced biochemical and thermochemical technologies, supports local and regional biomass mobilisation, and aligns with key EU policy goals under the Fit for 55 and Circular Economy Action Plan. As a drop-in solution, bio-MEG integrates seamlessly into existing industrial applications and recycling systems, notably in PET packaging and polyester textiles. Likewise, the strong involvement of stakeholders, policy support, and innovation-driven production (e.g., UPM's Leuna plant) demonstrates the potential for scalable, sustainable, and regionally anchored bioeconomy models. Furthermore, the case study underscores the systemic and institutional foundations supporting the scalability of bio-MEG. The power-interest matrix identifies MEG-reliant industries, such as textile and packaging sectors, as the most influential actors due to their control over downstream integration, with companies like Coca-Cola and VAUDE already incorporating bio-MEG into flagship products. On the production side, initiatives such as UPM's BioPura™ facility in Leuna (Germany), with a planned capacity of 220,000 tonnes per year and €1.18 billion in investment, exemplify industrial commitment to lignocellulosic bio-MEG at scale. The stakeholder mapping also highlights the role of public finance (e.g., Nordic Investment Bank's €200 million loan to UPM) and EU funding mechanisms (e.g., Horizon Europe support for Avantium) in de-risking early-stage commercialisation. Despite a 20-43% cost premium over fossil-based MEG, bio-MEG's potential to reduce GHG emissions by up to 69.5% compared to oil-derived MEG (Zhao et al., 2021) strengthens its profile under EU climate goals. However, the case also reveals critical gaps in LCA data, particularly on biodiversity, land-use change, and social impact metrics, which must be addressed through targeted research and transparent reporting frameworks to fully validate bio-MEG's sustainability claims.

The **bio-methanol** case study can be considered a good practice example for multiple reasons. To begin with, a variety of wastes and residues, including MSW, can be used to produce bio-methanol through gasification. MSW is a heterogeneous waste stream, consisting of, e.g., plastic, glass, metals, and paper, making it a complex stream to process, which is why it is currently primarily landfilled or incinerated. Diverting MSW to the production of bio-methanol could contribute to meeting the targets set in the EU Landfill Directive and Waste Framework Directive, which seek to increase the re-use and recycling rates of MSW. At the same time, the production of bio-methanol could play a role in the defossilisation of the chemical industry. At the moment, over 97% of the approximately 98 million tonnes of methanol produced worldwide relies on fossil

feedstocks (mainly natural gas and coal). Until 2028, the global demand for methanol is expected to rise to 131.06-160.98 million tonnes (based on a compound annual growth rate of 3.7-6.4%). Replacing fossil methanol with waste-based methanol could significantly reduce the demand for fossil feedstocks and lower the corresponding GHG emissions, which aligns with policies like Fit for 55. Several other environmental benefits of bio-methanol production (compared to the production of fossil methanol) were identified with respect to impacts on ozone depletion, acidification, and air quality. Industrial actors like Enerkem, GIDARA Energy and DOPS RT readily recognise the opportunities associated with bio-methanol production and invest in projects aimed at scaling up their production for both energy and non-energy applications. Examples of recommendations to upscale the bio-methanol value chain include bridging the price gap between fossil-based and waste-based methanol (i.e., by increasing the price of fossil products or decreasing the price of the bio-based/waste-based alternative), the development of infrastructure that facilitates the use of waste by the industry, and the installation of a mechanism to ensure that the rewards of valorising waste are allocated to the parties involved in a fair manner.

Recommendations from the case studies:

To foster the growth and deployment of bio-based chemicals in Europe, it is crucial to ensure adequate public financing for first-of-a-kind production facilities. Targeted financial support at this early stage of technological development can mitigate investment risk and encourage industrial uptake. Moreover, strategic collaboration with the sustainable finance sector is recommended to help design effective market-based incentives that align with long-term sustainability goals. In parallel, enhancing the resilience of bio-based value chains—including secure access to biomass, flexible production systems, and diversified end-use markets—will be essential to ensure their contribution to long-term societal and climate objectives.

In value chains that utilise secondary resources, efforts should be made to establish robust after-use markets to facilitate the circular flow of materials. Similarly, to support the use of agricultural and industrial residues, the necessary infrastructure must be developed. These measures not only enhance resource efficiency but also contribute meaningfully to the broader transition toward a circular economy. Additional good practices include the clear articulation of the specific challenges that the bio-based sector aims to address, along with conducting regular “reality checks” of policy and market ambitions. This ensures that proposed strategies are both actionable and grounded in the practical constraints of current systems.

Raising awareness of the advantages of the sustainable bioeconomy—and the environmental and societal risks associated with continued reliance on fossil-based systems—remains a vital educational priority. Targeted education and outreach can help shift consumer perceptions and promote broader public support for sustainable innovations.

At the technical level, the harmonisation of sustainability assessment practices across the value chain is needed. The establishment of common EU-level guidance will help standardise the currently diverse range of systems, scopes, and methodological approaches used to evaluate bio-based products. The continued development and application of the **Safe and Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD)** framework are recommended as a means to build comprehensive knowledge on the sustainability performance of bio-based chemicals. This approach supports the integration of environmental, social, and economic considerations into product development from the outset.

Guidance documents such as **European Standard EN18027** provide important methodological support for conducting comparative LCAs between bio-based and fossil-based products. Furthermore, revising the European Commission’s Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) method, particularly in relation to biogenic carbon accounting, will be critical to ensuring fair and consistent comparisons across product categories.

Finally, the implementation of the EU’s **Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability** is an important step in reducing chemical pollution and protecting human health. This strategy reinforces the commitment to transition towards safe and sustainable chemicals, underpinned by principles such as SSbD and circularity. To maximise the effectiveness of individual policy instruments, a **unified EU-level strategic vision for the bio-based chemical sector** is needed. This should include measurable targets, timelines, and a cross-sectoral implementation roadmap that guides both public and private investments.

4.4 Policy recommendations to stimulate transition and enhance resource efficiency

In the former sections, several recommendations were made in relation to policy measures that can be taken to stimulate the transition to a more circular and sustainable chemicals sector in the EU. The current section presents in greater detail the policy instruments identified in the case studies as good practice examples, followed by a discussion of policy instruments that can be implemented in the near future and for which potentially details are already being worked out by the EU and national governments. This section also links to the work done in WP5 of SUSTRACK, where policies have been extensively reviewed and detailed policy recommendations are produced, taking account of extensive reviews of literature, several exchanges with stakeholders in the IMPLEMENT workshops and through a survey consultation.

An overview of the good policy examples and the recommended new policy instruments is presented in Table 4. The policy instruments are linked to the challenges for the transition they address and that were discussed in the former section, and also to the CBBE targets they contribute to (see Appendix 2).

Table 4 Overview of policy instruments identified to tackle barriers and/or stimulate transition to CBBE

Policy instrument	Existing Good example instrument or proposed or recommended policy instrument?	Type of instrument (direct regulation, market based instrument, or other) (see Appendix 1)	Challenge addressed	Contribution to CBBE target (see Appendix 2)
Quota for non-fossil feedstock share in production, leading to a phase out of fossils in e.g., 2050	Recommended policy instrument, (readily existing as a good example in other sectors such as in the Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive for plastics)	Could become direct regulation, but could also be linked to public procurement	1) Low cost-competitiveness of bio-based chemicals 2) Absence of dedicated regulatory support for bio-based chemical products 3) Decarbonization remains the primary focus of existing policies	1) Reduce GHG emissions 2) Improve resource efficiency
Sustainability criteria for biomass to be eligible to the quota (e.g., EU Renewable Materials Directive following the EU Renewable Energy Directive)	Recommended policy instrument, (could follow the good example of “Duurzaamheidskader biogrondstoffen” (in English: Sustainability framework biological feedstocks), which is currently implemented in the Netherlands)	Direct regulation (could be coupled to e.g., voluntary approaches, such as certification, and market-based instruments)	1) Absence of dedicated regulatory support for bio-based chemical products	1) Reduce GHG emissions 2) Improve resource efficiency
Innovation subsidy for the development and market penetration of non-fossil chemicals	Recommended policy instrument, (some good examples already exist, such as the “DEI+ vergassing van reststromen” (in English: subsidy gasification of residual streams) in the Netherlands)	Market-based instrument	1) Limited access to financing for early-stage technologies 2) Low cost-competitiveness of bio-based chemicals	1) Reduce GHG emissions 2) Improve resource efficiency 3) Decoupling

Product subsidy for non-fossil chemicals (e.g., green VAT, reduced tax rate)	Recommended policy instrument	Market-based instrument	1) Limited access to financing for early-stage technologies 2) Low cost-competitiveness of bio-based chemicals	1) Reduce GHG emissions 2) Improve resource efficiency
Carbon tax on the use of fossil feedstocks and low-value biomass uses for chemicals production	Recommended policy instrument	Market-based instrument	1) Low cost-competitiveness of bio-based chemicals 2) Decarbonization remains the primary focus of existing policies	1) Reduce GHG emissions 2) Improve resource efficiency 3) Decoupling
Innovation subsidy for developing low-risk chemicals and toxic-free products according to EU-SSbD-framework and decontamination technologies	Recommended policy instrument	Market-based instrument	1) Limited access to financing for early-stage technologies 2) Barrier to circularity due to hazardous substances	1) Reduce GHG emissions 2) Improve resource efficiency
Thresholds for key Substances of Concern in products (that inhibit reuse, recycling etc.)	Recommended policy instrument	Direct regulation	1) Barrier to circularity due to hazardous substances	2) Improve resource efficiency 3) Decoupling
SCIP Extension of EU SCIP database to chemicals inhibiting circularity	Recommended policy instrument (Based on existing SCIP database)	Direct regulation	1) Barrier to circularity due to hazardous substances	2) Improve resource efficiency 3) Decoupling
Extended REACH criteria for chemicals permission that consider recycling etc. of products	Recommended policy instrument (Based on existing REACH criteria)	Direct regulation	1) Barrier to circularity due to hazardous substances	2) Improve resource efficiency 3) Decoupling

The first proposed policy instrument concerns the implementation of a quota for a non-fossil feedstock share in the production of chemicals, leading to a phase out of fossils in e.g., by 2050. During the stakeholder discussions in the IMPLEMENT workshop, several strengths of this policy instrument were brought up. First of all, quotas are considered an effective, powerful instrument given the urgency of environmental issues facing the EU (and the relevance that the EU is losing globally), as it allows the authorities to directly steer towards targets of reduced fossil feedstock utilisation. Besides that, the introduction of a quota for non-fossil feedstock in chemicals can commence with a small percentage (e.g., 5% or 10% of the product volume/carbon content), and consequently be built up in small steps. This gradual transition would allow producers of chemicals to get acquainted with and subsequently adopt new production practices over time. Furthermore, quotas can be integrated in legislation that is readily implemented at the EU level, either sector-specific or sector-agnostic, such as the Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive (PPWD), End-of-life Vehicles Regulation (ELVR) and Eco-design for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR). The PPWD, for example, lays down targets to increase the use of bio-based feedstock, as well as for recycled content, in plastic packaging. Similarly, such targets could be set for the production of chemicals. Nonetheless, it must be noted that the implementation of quotas is highly complex, especially for small and medium enterprises (SMEs), considering the existence of separate targets for recycled, bio-based and captured carbon as alternative non-fossil feedstocks. Additionally, industrial solutions for bio-based alternatives to conventional fossil products need to be sufficiently mature before quotas can be implemented successfully. Despite promising developments (see e.g., the good examples of bio-MEG and bio-methanol), bio-based solutions do not yet exist for all chemical applications.

Building on the above recommendation, it is suggested to implement sustainability criteria for biomass to be eligible for to bio-based quota. While mandatory sustainability requirements are readily implemented for energy applications (i.e., EU RED), bio-based materials and products are

excluded from this regulatory framework. As such, following the RED, a Renewable Materials Directive is called for. A major benefit of such a directive is that well-designed sustainability criteria will allow for the better use of the biomass readily produced and reduce the land use (change) related GHG emissions. Certification schemes and labels can be used by producers of biomass to demonstrate compliance with these sustainability criteria. In turn, the Green Claims Directive will be key in ensuring the transparency and trustworthiness of sustainability claims. A study from nova-Institute shows that a factor four increase (from 5.5% in the EU27 in 2023 to 20%) would be feasible (Carus et al., 2025). Additionally, when requiring high product quality standards that extend the lifetime of products, this could contribute to a reduced demand for new products. However, biomass is scarce, and competition between sectors is high. Carus et al. (2025) calculated that the planet cannot provide sufficient amounts of sustainable biomass to meet the rising demands for energy, chemicals, and beyond. As such, CO₂ utilisation (CCU) and recycling are needed to meet demands. Simultaneously, the creation of cascaded value chains could aid in addressing the biomass availability question. Also, it was commented that Annex IX of the RED is currently too prescriptive, and that it must be ensured that the criteria are feedstock agnostic.

Additionally, two types of subsidies can support the transition from fossil to bio-based chemicals: innovation subsidies and product subsidies. For innovation subsidies, to begin with, some examples of good practice already exist. In the Netherlands, for example, the “DEI+ vergassing van reststromen” (in English: subsidy gasification of residual streams) can be requested for the execution of a demonstration project, aimed at the gasification of waste streams (i.e., biogenic, or mixed). The installation converts these residues to renewable energy carriers, such as green gas, biofuel, or a chemical. The entire gasification chain, including pre-treatment, torrefaction, gasification, and purification, is eligible. Whereas innovation subsidies could stimulate R&D efforts for the sustainable production of chemicals, it was commented that, as long as there is no positive business case when operational, such a subsidy will not be sufficient for market uptake. To this end, OPEX subsidies are still needed in addition. This is where product subsidies (e.g., as green VAT or reduced tax rate) can be supported. By means of illustration, Spain has introduced fossil plastic taxes, which seem to be quite effective instruments in promoting alternative feedstocks and incentivising the reduction of overall amounts of packaging. For both subsidy types, however, it is indicated that subsidies are not sustainable, and that eventually the industry must be profitable to survive.

Furthermore, it is recommended to introduce a carbon tax for the use of fossil feedstocks and low-value biomass for the production of chemicals. As a result, products based on fossil feedstocks as well as low-value biomass applications become more expensive and therefore less attractive for consumers, incentivising producers to shift to high-value applications of biomass. When implementing this policy instrument, it must be clear which applications of biomass are considered low and high value, respectively, and to penalise the low-value applications accordingly. In the legal sustainability framework for biological resources that is being developed in the Netherlands, a distinction is made between three categories of biomass applications. First, policy for low-value applications (i.e., low temperature heat, light road transport and electricity) will focus on phasing out these applications. Second, policy for transition applications (i.e., air and maritime transport, heavy road transport and high temperature heat) will focus on the temporary use of biological resources, followed by the use of renewable alternatives. Thirdly, policy for high-value applications (i.e., materials and feedstocks) will focus on upscaling (Dutch Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management, 2020). A similar classification could be utilized at EU level, serving as a guidance for the introduction of taxes. Thereby, it was mentioned that the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) for the chemical industry should facilitate in creating an international level playing field. In this context, achieving international policy coherence is essential. Enhanced cooperation on regulatory frameworks will prevent carbon leakage and protect EU industry from relocation pressures, particularly to regions with lower

environmental and safety standards. Instruments like CBAM should be reinforced with broader trade and compliance diplomacy.

Several regulatory and incentive-based instruments are emerging that specifically address the toxicological and circularity barriers to bio-based and recycled chemicals. These are aligned with the EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS) and Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) framework and can further stimulate the transition to a circular bio-based economy.

Innovation subsidy for developing low-risk chemicals and toxic-free products according to the EU-SSbD framework, including decontamination technologies. This policy instrument aims to accelerate the development of inherently safer chemicals and decontamination technologies by providing dedicated innovation funding aligned with the SSbD principles. While existing innovation subsidies often target decarbonisation or feedstock innovation, there remains a gap in public funding for process design innovations that reduce toxicity and enhance recyclability. This could be addressed through dedicated calls under Horizon Europe or national green innovation programmes, focusing on non-toxic product design, enzyme-based decontamination methods, or novel solvent systems for separation and purification. Such targeted innovation support is critical, as studies show that hazardous chemical additives and contaminants significantly hinder the reuse and recycling of plastics, packaging, and textiles (ECHA, 2023). Moreover, reducing hazardous inputs at the design stage helps prevent legacy contamination in future secondary raw materials.

Thresholds for key Substances of Concern in products (that inhibit reuse and recycling). Introducing clear and enforceable thresholds for key Substances of Concern (SoCs) in products is a direct regulatory measure with high leverage for circularity. It targets the root causes of downcycling and incineration of potentially recyclable materials. Under this instrument, limits would be set for the presence of persistent, bioaccumulative, and toxic substances, endocrine disruptors, and other critical SoCs in products where these substances inhibit high-quality recycling. Examples include flame retardants in plastics or adhesives in composite packaging. These thresholds could build upon the restrictions developed under REACH and be integrated into eco-design requirements under the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR). This policy would be particularly relevant for drop-in biochemicals like bio-MEG, which can be incorporated into packaging and textiles—two sectors where SoCs currently limit circularity. If aligned with market surveillance, such thresholds can drive product redesign while avoiding unfair burdens on bio-based alternatives.

SCIP Extension, i.e., expanding the EU SCIP database to include chemicals inhibiting circularity. The current SCIP (Substances of Concern In articles as such or in complex objects (Products)) database, managed by ECHA, focuses on substances meeting the criteria of Article 57 of REACH. A logical next step is the extension of SCIP to track not only hazardous substances but also **circularity-inhibiting substances**, such as substances that prevent effective mechanical or chemical recycling due to stability, reactivity, or incompatibility with separation technologies. This extension would require the identification and classification of such substances and would enable both policymakers and recyclers to access improved data on material flows and contamination risks. It would also support Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) schemes in prioritising safe material loops and incentivising the use of recyclable, non-toxic inputs. For bio-based products like bio-MEG derivatives, SCIP expansion would provide critical transparency, helping manufacturers differentiate truly circular materials from those with hidden barriers to recycling.

Finally, an extended REACH criteria for chemicals permission to include recyclability and circular use potential. While REACH already provides a framework for chemical safety assessment, it does not systematically evaluate substances based on their **impact on circular material flows**. Extending REACH criteria to consider recyclability, potential for reuse, and the

presence of irreversible contaminants would align chemical management with the goals of the circular economy. This extension could take the form of additional annexes or updated guidance documents that require registrants to provide information not only on toxicity and exposure, but also on chemical compatibility with recycling systems and degradability under industrial conditions. In practice, this could lead to authorisation refusals for substances that block closed-loop systems without providing essential functional benefits. For example, the presence of unremovable plasticisers or cross-linking agents in otherwise recyclable polymers could be considered a negative factor in REACH evaluations. Such changes would strongly incentivise safer design choices across both fossil and bio-based chemical value chains.

5 PLASTICS SECTOR

5.1 Short description of the sector and the 3 case studies

The majority of plastics in use today are virgin plastics derived from crude oil or natural gas. Since 1970, global plastic consumption has increased more than twentyfold, reaching 460 million tonnes per year by 2019. Projections indicate that, without significant policy changes, global plastics consumption could nearly triple to 1,231 million tonnes by 2060 (OECD, 2022). By 2050, plastic consumption in the EU alone is expected to further increase by 30% as compared to 2019 (Statista, 2025). Of the 353 million tonnes of plastic waste generated worldwide in 2019, only 9% underwent recycling. An additional 19% was subjected to incineration, while nearly 50% was directed to landfills (OECD, 2022). The remaining 22% entered the waste stream without proper management, including uncontrolled deposition in dumps, open burning or environmental leakage. Microplastics in ecosystems have large negative impacts on habitats, species and human health.

For the plastics sector, three case studies were selected and extensively described and analysed. These are a polylactic acid-based plastic (PLA) case, polypropylene made of used cooking oil (UCO) and a cellulose acetate case made of wood pulp.

Poly(lactic acid) (PLA) is a bio-based and, under controlled composting conditions, biodegradable thermoplastic aliphatic polyester (Taib *et al.*, 2023). The building block for PLA is lactic acid. Lactic acid is produced by bacterial fermentation of carbohydrates or chemical synthesis, although the former predominates. The first synthesis of lactic acid was recorded in 1845 by French chemist Théophile-Jules Pelouze. In 1932, Wallace Carothers *et al.* developed a method to polymerise lactide into low-density PLA by heating lactic acid under vacuum while removing condensed water (Masutani and Kimuara, 2014). Over the past decades, PLA has undergone significant development and has been used in a variety of fields. PLA stores the carbon of biogenic origin that was taken up from the atmosphere by the plant in its growth phase and reemits it during composting, creating a carbon-neutral cycle. PLA is not biodegradable in landfills or through home composting, so for PLA not to cause a waste problem, it must be taken to the right sites at its end of life. Only through industrial composting or anaerobic digestion under thermophilic conditions is PLA biodegradable. Easily processed on standard plastics equipment, PLA can be used to manufacture moulded parts, fibres and films, consumer goods and is the most used filament for 3D-printing, the main applications for PLA can be categorised as following:

- Consumer goods: disposable tableware, cutlery, housings for kitchen appliances and electronics (PLA is not suitable for microwaves due to its low glass temperature).
- Agricultural: mulch films, filaments.
- Clinical: anchors, screws, plates, pins, rods, mesh.

Polypropylene (PP) represents one of the most widely used plastics in Europe thanks to its versatility. Motivated by the growing demand for plastics and related concerns about their climate impact, bio-based plastics have attracted attention as alternatives for petrochemical plastics. In this sense, bio-based PP could be a significant alternative to petrochemical PP. It is estimated that currently around 90% of cooking oils and fats used in the EU are produced from vegetable oils. According to EU estimations, the potential UCO to be collected is around 8 L

UCO/capita/year. In the EU-28, the total potential UCO available from the gastronomy sector, food processors and households is estimated at around 4 Mt per year. Moreover, China supplies more than a third (34%) of Europe's UCO imports, while almost a fifth (19%) comes from the major palm oil producers, Malaysia and Indonesia combined.¹ According to European Bioplastics, commercialisation of bio-based PP started in 2019. Therefore, the market is still at its nascent stage, and it is expected to quadruple by 2025. Based on application, the market is segmented into building & construction, automotive, consumer goods, packaging and others.

Cellulose acetate (CA) is a modified natural polymer, or bio-based polymer, with a rich history and high versatility, observable through various applications and sectors (GVR, 2024). In 1865, the reaction between cellulose and acetic anhydride, forming cellulose acetate, was first observed (Schützenberger, 1865) and further processing of CA was enabled with the discovery of the first soluble forms in 1903 (Kidder Maede, McCormack, Clark, Sclater, & Lamborn, 1905). Since then, CA has been used for producing films for photography, man-made fibres for clothing and filter production, frames for eyeglasses, precursors for coatings and paints, plastic materials, packaging as well as medical applications (Bardy, Dürig, Lee, & Li, 2017; Teixeira, Paiva, Amorim, & Felgueiras, 2020; Teixeira, et al., 2021; Wolfs & Meier, 2021; GVR, 2024; Sebruyns, Van de Perre, & Hölter, 2024).

CA can be produced through a variety of production processes, whereby the most used process uses wood pulp and acetic acid as inputs (Bardy, Dürig, Lee, & Li, 2017). By using wood, the carbon stored is integrated into the bio-based polymer and retained throughout the lifecycle of the final product. Together with PHA, CA is among the best-in-class materials concerning biodegradation time requirements. CA biodegrades in natural environments such as soil, water and marine ecosystems (Kubiwicz & Booth, 2017; Slezak, Krzystek, Puchalski, Krucińska, & Sitarski, 2023; James, et al., 2024a; Yu & Flury, 2024). These properties make CA a versatile material to tackle plastic pollution and displace fossil-based polymers across a range of sectors. Some potential (and continued) applications include:

- Consumer goods: textiles, frames for eyeglasses, photography films, packaging materials, cosmetics, electronics
- Chemical industry: precursors for paints and coatings, filtration materials, membranes
- Medical applications: artificial fibres, active ingredient carrier for medicines, plasters, gauze bandages

5.2 Main challenges and opportunities in the transition to a CBBE in the plastics sector

The challenges for the transition of the mainly linear and strong fossil-based sector towards a more circular bio-based plastics sector are described in this section. These are based on the perspectives derived from the detailed analysis of the three case studies and the different insights obtained during the SUSTRACK DESIGN and IMPLEMENT workshops with stakeholders, both specific to the case studies and the wider EU plastics sector.

¹ [Europe's imports of dubious 'used' cooking oil set to rise, fuelling deforestation](#)

The challenges can be categorised according to market, sustainability and policy aspects.

Market dimension challenges

The market dimension of biopolymers faces several obstacles, primarily the difficulty in scaling up production capacity due to bureaucratic hurdles, limited availability of land for production facilities, policy ambiguity and cost competitiveness compared to fossil-based alternatives. High initial costs and prolonged timeframes required to bring products to the market further impede market expansion. This is exacerbated by policy incoherence, whereby regulation may apply to some products but not others, or where a blanket suspicion is put across materials that have little in common, as is, for instance, the case with the Single Use Plastics Directive (SUPD). Over time, such regulation is referenced in newer directives and policies, which leads to compounding of the uncertainty and ambiguity, pre-empting the necessary confidence that is required to implement large investments in the space. The resulting uncertainty renders the market space for biopolymers less attractive because of fragmentation. This is why a harmonisation of existing policy initiatives and their underlying definitions and classifications is desperately needed.

The limited availability of bio-based raw materials, combined with the higher production costs of biopolymers, poses a major challenge for the bioplastics industry. To mitigate these challenges, stakeholders involved in the SUSTRACK co-creation activities advocate for governmental assistance to streamline bureaucratic processes, reduce market space uncertainty, and hence allow for investments to increase production capacity. Moreover, there is a consensus on the need for a clearer definition of the chemical and physical properties of all polymers, bio-based and fossil-based, to guide research towards viable applications. This would allow us to highlight the best materials for specific use cases or specific strategic ambitions. Some stakeholders, for instance, noted that PLA is unsuitable for certain sectors, such as textiles, while being more suited for others. In the case of CA, other stakeholders mentioned that existing regulations and policy incoherence are major obstacles to entering new business segments.

The challenge of the lower cost-competitiveness of the bio-based plastics sector is largely due to the lack of monetisation of environmental costs. This is further compounded by market-related bottlenecks, including the need for increased investment, long time-to-market periods, and limited availability of well-equipped specialised tech parks and plants accessible to (small) third parties. Additionally, there is a recognised lack of market pull measures to encourage the willingness to use products containing circular materials.

Sustainability dimension challenges

There are several challenges related to the sustainability dimension of biopolymers. Most notably, biodegradation of bio-based polymers and testing methodologies used are at the forefront of these challenges. There are differences in the ability of bio-based polymers to biodegrade in different environments, highlighted, for instance, by Yu and Flury (2024), and the speed at which they biodegrade in these respective environments (James, et al., 2024a; James, Ward, Hahn, Thrope, & Reddy, 2024a). However, this is oftentimes not reflected or captured in existing certifications and established labelling, such as “readily biodegradable”, and may mislead consumers.

At the same time, (i) the criteria of the methods used to measure biodegradation as defined in Commission Regulation (EU) 2023/2055 are based on an approach that is so precautionary that there is a disproportionate risk for biodegradable bio-based materials to not pass this test as time passes, and, more importantly, (ii) thresholds for biodegradation time frames are based on materials other than polymers, but then arbitrarily applied to polymers by policymakers, rendering them inadequate. For example, under the application of current testing criteria, even natural products, such as walnuts, blueberry seeds and lignin-containing materials, may not qualify as biodegradable (McDonough, et al., 2017; Kwon, Zambrano, Pawlak, & Venditti, 2021). This combination provides unrealistic testing criteria and an environment of uncertainty related to the tests to conduct, both of which are not only a sustainability challenge, but also an aspect related to the market dimension. This leads to the disqualification of promising bio-based and biodegradable polymers before they even enter the market, and hence suppresses the development of viable alternatives to fossil-based polymers.

From the case of Polypropylene (PP), it also became clear collection and disposal of used cooking oil can still be significantly improved, as it is still unsustainably disposed of in the environment, leading in several places to contamination of water resources, harming aquatic life, and clogging drainage systems. Strengthening regulations to ensure its proper collection, recycling, and conversion into bio-based products such as PP can help mitigate these negative impacts and support sustainable waste management. Incentive schemes, like setting minimum bio-based content targets for key plastic applications, are needed to create market pull. Moreover, improving the separate collection of organic household waste across all EU member states would increase the availability of high-quality biowaste for applications such as bioplastics production.

Policy dimension challenges

One of the main policy-related challenges mentioned by industry stakeholders is the absence of a harmonised definition for bio-based plastics and polymers, which is crucial for setting standards, certification schemes, and effectively regulating the market. To address this issue, stakeholders recommend enhanced governmental backing, particularly through the revision and harmonisation of existing legislation and their underlying set of definitions and classifications. Harmonisation is proposed for policy frameworks such as the SUPD, the Microplastics Directive and directives related to polymer use in the agriculture sector. Such legislative updates would significantly reduce the uncertainty in the policy space, facilitate the broader adoption of biodegradable plastics, and thereby promote market growth and sustainability, stimulating the transition towards a circular bio-based economy.

Another closely related aspect is policy fragmentation, which is in part related to the absence of clear definitions and classifications. Policy fragmentation makes producers of bio-based polymers to constantly assess (and fear) whether they are affected by specific policies, and if so, what that means for their business prospects and potential testing requirements. This generates a large degree of uncertainty and drives the costs of monitoring and testing for bio-based products, which adds to the competitive disadvantage compared to fossil-based products.

Governmental support in a range of areas is also critical, especially when it comes to supporting the circularity of bio-based polymers. For instance, while recycling infrastructure for conventional, fossil-based plastics is well established, recycling technologies and infrastructure

for bio-based polymers are scarce and incentives for development are largely absent (Akinsemolu, Idowu, & Onyeaka, 2024). Addressing the beginning and the end of the value chain is hence crucial in the development of an environment that shall enable the transition towards a CBBE. Moreover, PLA stakeholders have identified a significant challenge in the form of insufficient governmental support for the utilisation of compostable plastics in food and soil applications. This lack of support adversely impacts both the market viability and the sustainability of PLA. Specifically, for the PP plastics generation, it would help to better target the collection of used cooking oils from households, which is still very inefficient. It underscores the need for improved waste management policies and greater public awareness. Industries that use PP derived from used cooking oils also face challenges due to the lack of clear market regulations, which are essential to ensure product quality, uphold sustainability standards, and promote fair competition within the bio-based plastics sector. Moreover, the absence of favourable policies, such as incentives for the use of renewable carbon, acts as a barrier to the development and wider adoption of bio-based plastics.

5.3 Recommendations and good practice examples

Overall, the three case studies can be seen as good practice examples of production systems that contribute to the transition to a more sustainable plastic sector. From the case study analysis and the SUSTRACK DESIGN and IMPLEMENT many more specific recommendations and good practice examples were obtained to address the different barriers discussed previously.

Good practice examples:

The stakeholders highlight several policies as exemplary practices in promoting sustainability within the plastics industry. Notable among these are the EU Plastics Strategy, the Circular Economy Action Plan and the EU Policy Framework on Bio-based, Biodegradable and Compostable Plastics of 2022. Additionally, Directive (EU) 2015/720 on lightweight plastic carrier bags can be cited as effective measures. These policies collectively contribute to the advancement of sustainable practices by setting clear guidelines and standards for the use and management of plastics. Directive (EU) 2019/904, known as the Single-Use Plastics Directive (SUPD), is regarded as effective, although there is strong evidence that suggests that reductions have already commenced before the regulation entered into force (Hanke, et al., 2025). Conclusive evidence of its effectiveness remains to be developed.

Recommendations from the case studies:

To further enhance sustainability efforts, stakeholders propose the introduction of mandatory bio-based content requirements to complement the existing mandatory recycled content in the Packaging and Packaging Waste Legislation (PPWL) and the End-of-Life Vehicles (ELV) Regulation. One critical contribution is the emphasis on the need for a coherent, fact-based definition of bio-based polymers across all policy frameworks, replacing politically driven definitions (such as those in the SUPD) with scientifically accurate classifications that distinguish between different types of polymers.

Moreover, they also advocate for increased financial support from the government, including incentives for bio-based materials and assistance in scaling up technologies with a Technology

Readiness Level (TRL) above 5. Furthermore, establishing a legally binding framework with clear sustainability criteria and incentives for labels and externally audited third-party certification systems is deemed necessary. Lastly, to strengthen the bioeconomy strategy, stakeholders recommend removing unnecessary constraints, whereby some constraints are material-specific. PLA stakeholders regard the limitation to marine biodegradable materials only as a constraint, while CA producers mention policy fragmentation and excessively precautionary criteria for biodegradability. The latter applies to almost all biopolymers, including PLA, indicating that an objective, yet well-intended, revision of testing methods and criteria would benefit the sector.

5.4 Policy recommendations to stimulate transition and enhance resource efficiency

In the former sections, several recommendations were already made in relation to policy measures that can be taken to stimulate the transition to a more circular and sustainable plastics sector in the EU. In this section, we present in greater detail the policy instruments that were (i) identified based on case study findings, as good practice examples, together with (ii) policy instruments identified based on literature review, both of which could be implemented soon and for which potentially details are already being worked out by EU and national governments. Literature review-based instruments proposed in this section are based on the work done in WP5 of the SUSTRACK. Here, policies have been extensively reviewed and detailed policy recommendations are produced, taking account of extensive reviews of literature, several exchanges with stakeholders in the DEPLOY workshops and through a survey consultation. These policy instruments will be used to supplement the case study findings and to integrate some of the ongoing work at the EU level.

The overview of case study-based policy examples and the literature review-based policy instruments are presented in Table 5 Overview of policy instruments identified to tackle barriers and/or stimulate CBBE transition. The policy instruments are linked to the challenges for the transition they address and which were discussed in the former section, and to the CBBE targets to which they contribute. A brief description of the instruments is provided below the table.

Table 5 Overview of policy instruments identified to tackle barriers and/or stimulate CBBE transition

Policy instrument	Existing good example instrument or proposed or recommended policy instrument	Type of instrument (direct regulation, market-based instrument, or other)	Challenge addressed	Contribution to CBBE
Quota for use of recycled material	Recommended policy instrument	Direct regulation and/or market-based instrument based on the implementation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Lack of transparency and traceability (greenwashing) 2) Lack of supporting infrastructure 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Improve resource efficiency 2) Reduce GHG emissions
Increased carbon efficiency (bio-based waste utilization and prevention)	Proposed policy instrument	Direct regulation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Address end-of-life challenges related to bio-based materials 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Improve resource efficiency 2) Waste reduction and increased circularity 3) Reduce GHG emissions

Ecodesign criteria	Proposed policy instrument	Direct regulation and/or market-based instrument depending on the implementation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Lack of transparency and traceability (greenwashing) 2) Lack of supporting infrastructure 3) Technical challenges in bioplastics' end-of-life processing 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Improve end-of-life treatment 2) Resource use efficiency
Sustainability criteria and cap	Good example instrument	Direct regulation, to be informed and developed in collaboration with industry partners	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Lack of transparency and traceability (greenwashing) 2) Lack of supporting infrastructure 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Comparability of materials 2) Reduce GHG emissions 3) Improve end-of-life treatment 4) Resource use efficiency
Innovation subsidy: circularity	Recommended policy instrument	Direct regulation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Lack of supporting infrastructure 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Reduce GHG emissions 2) Improve end-of-life treatment 3) Resource use efficiency
Carbon tax on polymers that are exclusively based on virgin fossil raw materials	Recommended policy instrument	Direct regulation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Difficulty to enter/penetrate market 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Improve resource efficiency 2) Decoupling
Forest carbon subsidy for sustainable forest biomass producers	Good example instrument	Direct regulation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Overuse of unsustainable forest biomass 2) Exploitation and degradation of forest ecosystems 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Increased uptake of sustainable forest management practices 2) Improve resource efficiency 3) Increase carbon storage/Reduce GHG emissions
Ban on intentionally added, non-biodegradable, microplastics in products	Recommended policy instrument	Direct regulation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Lack of transparency and traceability (greenwashing) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Reduce GHG emissions 2) Decoupling 3) Improve end-of-life treatment
Ban advertisement of non-biodegradable plastic products that exclusively use fossil-based raw materials	Recommended policy instrument	Direct regulation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Lack of transparency and traceability (greenwashing) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Reduce GHG emissions 2) Decoupling
Promote the development of recycling infrastructure for bio-based materials and provide the necessary funding	Recommended policy instrument	Direct regulation and/or market-based instrument depending on the implementation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Absence of recycling facilities for bio-based polymers 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Resource availability 2) Reduce GHG emissions 3) Increase circularity (reduces waste)

From the case study descriptions and also the IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY workshop stakeholder discussions, it became evident that certain new policy instruments are quite widely recommended to be introduced. Some of these recommendations overlap with the policies announced already,

such as PPWR and the EU Bioeconomy Strategy, to a large extent. In proposing additional policy instruments, thorough attention must be paid to their focus to ensure their effectiveness in achieving the desired outcome. Plastics and polymers were developed to serve a specific purpose, which means that bans or restrictions may cause more harm than good in the absence of feasible replacement materials. It is, however, important to note that excess plastic use should be avoided, and that predominantly bio-based and biodegradable materials should be favoured to tackle plastic pollution and the microplastic accumulation in the environment.

Several policies are directly regulated by the government and interventions. One such policy is the quota on the use of recycled material, which demands that producers incorporate a certain percentage of recycled plastics into their products. This quota could be applied to major sources of non-packaging plastic waste, such as construction materials, automotive and electrical and electronic devices. The quota itself, and the ramp up of its ambition, however, should consider the availability and quality of recycled material that is available for the satisfaction of the quota requirements.

The above highlights that the implementation of recycling quotas must be supported by adequate recycling infrastructure availability, which is the enabling factor for the achievement of recycling quotas. Especially for bio-based polymers, recycling infrastructure is underdeveloped or absent, putting these materials at a disadvantage and rendering the achievement of recycling quotas very challenging, if not impossible. This makes promoting the development of recycling infrastructure for bio-based materials and providing the necessary funding crucial for enhancing the sustainability aspect and supporting their integration into the recycling system.

The establishment of recycling infrastructure would also contribute to increasing carbon efficiency, or in other words, that carbon in the system is put to the most efficient use. At the moment, composting or incineration of materials makes so that carbon being lost into the carbon cycle in the form of CO₂, rendering these the least carbon efficient alternatives. The recycling of biopolymers, and a revision of existing regulations for their end-of-life management, has the potential to keep materials in the system for longer before the “exit” into the carbon cycle in the form of CO₂.

Another important aspect that was discussed is that sustainable alternatives are required and that reuse and repair are promoted over end-of-life treatment methods that take materials out of the system, such as incineration, landfill, or open dumping. The Ecodesign criteria set by the EU aim to improve the longevity of the products, including their repairability and recyclability, such as restricting coloured PET. It is initiatives like this, and smart requirements for single-use items until those can be phased out, that hold the largest potential to contribute to a sustainable transition towards a bio-based economy. Even if materials are regarded as “plastic pollution”, regulators must take account of the fact that there is the need for a transition phase where “less worse” materials are needed to shift the social system to a new normal. Policies must facilitate the transition towards this new normal rather than restricting environmentally friendlier, non-fossil-based materials before the new normal has been reached.

A subsidy for producers that use bio-based carbon supports the use of sustainable biomass and sends a signal downstream that longer-term demand for bio-based inputs is supported. This can be combined with a forest carbon subsidy, whereby forest owners receive rewards for increasing

carbon storage, which further promotes sustainable forest management. The upwards pressure for the production of sustainable, bio-based materials could be supplemented by a carbon tax on those materials that use exclusively fossil-based materials, disincentivising their use. Imposing a fossil carbon tax on products using exclusively fossil-based materials discourages the use of fossil resources within the market, and therefore forces producers to opt for a more sustainable option. This would support the expansion of sustainable raw material production and contribute to the EU's climate targets for the land use sector (LULUCF) at the same time.

Other policy instruments, recommended by the stakeholders, are collectively proposed to help boost the bioeconomy transition efforts. The restriction and ban on intentionally added non-biodegradable microplastics in products (e.g., cosmetics, toothpaste, etc.) aims to reduce microplastic pollution, which poses significant environmental and health risks. Additionally, the ban on the advertisement of plastic products that are exclusively fossil-based (similar to restrictions on cigarette advertising) aims to reduce consumer demand for fossil-based plastics and promote the adoption of more sustainable, bio-based and biodegradable alternatives.

Finally, efforts should be undertaken that assess policy impacts across multiple DGs at the EU level. Working groups sometimes develop regulations in parallel that may, unintentionally, lead to ambiguity, uncertainty, and, in the worst case, harmful outcomes for producers. The more we move into policymaking for sustainability and sustainable development, the more important it becomes to harmonise sustainability initiatives. It seems that, currently, an overall view on the interactions, referrals and interplay of the existing regulation is missing. Such an "overarching regulatory effort" might be the starting point to close gaps in regulation that are meant to foster a bio-based sector. This would be immensely beneficial to policymakers and producers alike and hold the potential to generate synergies across policy spaces. Lastly, this effort must acknowledge the fact that every decision is a trade-off, which becomes evident when thinking about the allocation of bio-based materials towards specific use cases. This is because there are simply not enough materials to satisfy all demand, which makes concepts like carbon efficiency even more important.

6 OVERALL CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This deliverable presents the main overall conclusions and recommendations derived through the implementation of 11 case studies selected in SUSTRACK, belonging to the four sectors that face critical challenges within the current fossil, linear economy: Construction, Textile, Chemical and Plastics. In the last chapter, some overarching conclusions and key recommendations are presented.

6.1 Overarching challenges

Market challenges

For all case studies, costs remain a major obstacle, making the bio-based and more circular products too expensive to compete with other mostly fossil-based products. This applies to the bio-based construction materials since the construction sector continues to experience rising material prices, and for bio-based alternatives, these cost pressures are often intensified. Higher initial costs may come from the materials themselves or from additional labour associated with installation, and also from higher insurance costs because bio-based materials are perceived to be less fire resistant. Also in the textile, plastics and chemical sector, the costs of bio-based products are higher. For example, for textiles, MMCFs from biomass or recycled fibres derived from discarded textiles are too expensive to compete with other mostly fossil and cotton-based fibres. Most of the fossil-based textiles, polymers and chemicals that dominate the markets remain considerably cheaper than the bio-based and/or recycled alternatives. Furthermore, the conventional products from the incumbent systems are entering the EU market from all over the world and are generally very low in price. In the case of textiles, even recycled materials are often more expensive than the virgin synthetic or cotton ones.

One overarching reason for the cost difference is that fossil-based chemicals benefit from decades of process optimisation and scale, while bio-based alternatives are often still in developmental stages, resulting in higher production costs. These new products often still need increased investments and are still coping with longer time-to-market periods. A second overarching factor is that secure and sufficient availability of bio-based raw materials is complex, and costs are often relatively high, certainly when large quantities are needed to reach minimal economies of scale. This applies to both residual and virgin biomass sources, but also to textile wastes to derive recycled fibres from. Moreover, the availability and price of biomass feedstocks are subject to fluctuations, especially given the growing competition from other sectors, including food, feed, and bioenergy. These pressures are expected to intensify toward 2050, potentially threatening feedstock security for the chemical, biopolymer, construction and MMCFs industries. A third overarching reason for higher cost relates to the difficulty in scaling up production capacity due to bureaucratic hurdles, limited availability of land for production facilities and also limited availability of well-equipped specialised tech parks and plants accessible to (smaller) companies.

The lack of harmonised standards in the construction sector for newer bio-based products is a significant problem in creating a level playing field with mainstream fossil- and mineral-based products on the market. Furthermore, many existing standards are outdated and fail to reflect current innovations in bio-based construction. As a result, bio-based products are often evaluated using inappropriate criteria, putting them at a disadvantage in areas such as fire performance,

thermal efficiency, life cycle assessments (including biogenic carbon and carbon storage), and carbon offsetting. A similar problem also applies to the plastics market, where a clearer definition of the chemical and physical properties of all polymers, bio-based and fossil-based, is needed to stimulate demand for certain types of bio-based alternatives towards viable applications in sub-markets. This would allow us to highlight the best materials for specific use cases or for specific strategic ambitions. A specific problem for bioplastics is also that currently the testing criteria for degradability are unrealistic, which leads to the disqualification of promising bio-based and biodegradable polymers before they even enter the market and hence suppresses the development of viable alternatives to fossil-based polymers.

The higher cost also goes together with an overall lack of market pull measures to encourage the willingness to use products containing bio-based and/or circular materials, which is largely due to the lack of monetisation of environmental costs. So generally, the success of bio-based and recycled alternatives hinges on the willingness of companies and consumers to pay a price premium. In the construction sector, specifically, the lack of market pull is further exacerbated by a lack of technical knowledge and practical experience with circular and/or bio-based construction materials. Designers, architects, and contractors often lack the training, confidence, or motivation to switch from conventional materials to bio-based alternatives. Since these professionals play a central role in determining which materials are used in building and renovation projects, their hesitancy significantly slows adoption.

Sustainability challenges

Bio-based and circular materials continue to face major challenges due to limited knowledge, low awareness, and common misconceptions about their performance, durability, and sustainability among potential end-users. As a result, awareness of alternative, eco-friendly solutions remains low, and progress toward more sustainable consumption and practices is slow. This is not only related to the mind-set of potential end-users of the products, but also the lack of policy guidance and existing norms and standards that are not easy to change.

For the transition, there is specific mention of the lack of transparency and traceability for products related to sustainability. This is mentioned specifically for textiles as a major problem, but is also a challenge for the biopolymers, bio-based building materials and biochemicals sectors. Sustainability certification could be a solution, however, for most of the 11 case studies presented, this is not always an easy solution since there are still many research and innovation and data gaps concerning sustainable practices in the whole supply chains. In the biopolymers sector, the claims on biodegradability are not well captured in existing certification or labelling, nor EU regulations. Environmental performance is the most frequently evaluated aspect, but there is limited capacity to adequately assess the economic and social dimensions due to data scarcity. The absence of a harmonised LCA methodology for bio-based products further complicates efforts to benchmark and improve their sustainability performance. In particular, inconsistencies in how biogenic carbon is accounted for, especially in cradle-to-gate versus cradle-to-grave assessments, create confusion. In the construction sector, for example, it is essential to incorporate the assessment of biogenic carbon accounting for both the long-term sequestration potential and the embodied emissions of materials such as timber through dynamic LCAs and improved land use indicators that reflect evolving land management practices. In the waste to methanol case, instead, the unequal allocation of sustainability benefits from waste valorisation is not clear.

Should the emission savings for diverting MSW away from incineration to methanol production be allocated to the municipality handling the waste? Or should the methanol producer gain these, as it can use these credits to compensate for the emissions at the plant level for generating methanol? A last point seen as a wide challenge is that labelling and certification also comes with extra cost, which are complicated to bear by the relatively many smaller companies that are involved in the innovative bio-based and/or more circular products, and they need to be added to the already high(er) production cost.

Policy challenges

Existing regulations still prioritise traditional materials and often overlook or inadequately accommodate the unique properties and performance benefits of bio-based and recycled materials. Bio-based materials differ significantly from geo- and fossil-based ones in terms of behaviour, environmental impact, and function. Yet, current regulations rarely reflect these differences, making it harder for such products to meet standard requirements and gain widespread acceptance. The current governance structure tends to tax labour more than goods and does not address environmental externality costs. There is still limited policy stimulation given to recyclability, lowering footprints and prevention of non-biodegradable microplastics losses to the environment, and no mechanisms are yet in place to prevent green washing, unfounded circularity and sustainability claims. One related aspect in this regard is that sufficiently clear and inclusive definitions for bio-based plastics, biopolymers and bio-based fibres make setting standards, certification and labelling more challenging.

Policies so far are not sufficiently addressing the beginning and the end of the value chain, which is crucial in the development of an environment that shall enable the transition towards a CBBE. This is illustrated through the biopolymer experience, pointing out that recycling infrastructure for conventional, fossil-based plastics is well established, recycling technologies and infrastructure for biopolymers are scarce, and incentives for development are largely absent. In the textiles sector, the same challenge applies where there is an urgent need to introduce guidelines on limiting the blending of different types of fossil and non-fossil fibres to make recyclability easier. Also, the handling of textile waste should be improved, including arranging for moving textile waste over EU borders, to facilitate the creation of economies of scale in more circular recycling chains. In the case of methanol from organic waste, it was found that a single, broadly supported EU political vision on the utilisation of waste does not exist. Another example is that at the EU level, gasification is mistakenly tied now to energy recovery in the waste processing hierarchy, which has readily obstructed licensing procedures for industrial bio-methanol plants. Overall, we can conclude that implementation of policy instruments addressing separate collection, post-separation and sorting of wastes into valuable waste components, such as UCO, bio-based construction products from demolitions, bio-based plastics and animal and vegetal-based textiles, can still be improved.

For all sectors, it was specifically indicated that the regulatory discrepancies between different policy domains and across EU countries are a major problem. Firstly, a lack of harmonisation in policymaking undermines investor confidence and obstructs the market expansion of novel bio-based and/or recycled products. Secondly, policy fragmentation forces producers of bio-based products such as biopolymers, MMCFs and bio-based building materials to constantly assess (and fear) whether they are affected by specific policies, and if so, what that means for their business

prospects and potential testing requirements in all different regions they sell. This generates a large degree of uncertainty and drives the costs of monitoring and testing for bio-based products, which adds to the competitive disadvantage compared to fossil-based products. The use of bio-based materials also faces differing legal restrictions and policy fragmentations between regions. For example, there are no harmonised Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs), safety standards, clear definitions and classifications across Europe. And this is despite the fact that harmonised definitions and classifications are crucial for setting standards, uniform certification schemes, and effectively regulating the markets.

One can also challenge whether ‘decarbonisation’ should be the primary focus of existing policy measures. In chemical sectors defossilisation could be a more appropriate since chemicals inherently rely on carbon-based building blocks, the goal should not be to eliminate carbon per se, but rather to replace fossil-derived carbon with renewable sources.

The last point in relation to access to markets for more sustainable products is the demand side. It was already pointed out that there is a lack of knowledge among potential producers and consumers about what is more and less sustainable. Policy can also play an important role in filling this gap in financing education and information campaigns.

6.2 Overarching policy recommendations

In this last subsection, overarching policy recommendations are presented. For more specific recommendations targeted specifically to the four sectors and 11 case studies the reader should still consult the dedicated chapters in this report.

The challenge of cost disparities is an issue challenging the market penetration of recycled products and sustainable bio-based alternatives to mostly fossil-based conventional products. This can be stimulated while tuning it well with requirements for improved sustainability. This can be addressed by a combined policy package. Financial policy instruments that can be recommended in this regard are reduced VAT for repaired products, recycled products and sustainable bio-based carbon products and penalties, through e.g. higher VAT or carbon tax on those materials that use exclusively fossil-based materials, disincentivising their use. All these instruments can only be effective in combination with measures through the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM). It is expected that initially the introduction of such a policy package will face lots of resistance, but will be effective in the end in stimulating behavioural change. There is also a risk that many companies will move their production outside the EU, and that it may lead to higher consumer prices, and this may make textiles less affordable for certain low-income groups. From a ‘just’ perspective, this may be undesired. Finally, it is recommended to design the instrument in such a way that it places responsibilities on all actors in the whole production chain. An additional positive outcome of a policy package of rewards and financial penalties could be that it will also attract more innovative end-of-life technologies to the EU. This does require better facilitation of the scaling of new technologies.

Also, digital product passports (DPPs) and/or Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) following more uniform standards, clear definitions and classifications across Europe were suggested quite widely, and this is in line with policy measures the EU is already working on. There is wide agreement on the need for instruments like DPPs or EPDs provided they are based on EU

harmonised standards, definitions and classifications. The latter should go together with data and method improvements on issues like recyclability, carbon footprints, embodied energy in products, (sustainable) energy use, water input and pollution prevention, land use, and use of fair and socially sustainable production approaches.

The Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) entered into force in July 2024 and applies in principle to almost all categories of physical products. It establishes a framework for setting ecodesign requirements on specific product groups. So far, this instrument has only been announced but not yet adopted in concrete legislation. The policy implementation details are, however, expected to become more concrete in 2025. The ESPR aims on the one hand to introduce mandatory durability, repairability and recyclability criteria for products. On the other hand, it also announces the introduction of the Digital Product Passport (DPP). With the ecodesign criteria, it is also recommended to create collaboration structures for certification and labelling, ensuring that sustainability claims are standardised and credible. From the case studies, it has become clear that expectations are high that these types of instruments contribute to the transition towards a CBBE, because they are expected to help to phase out unsustainable single-use items and support a stronger level playing field and market penetration of alternative, more circular and sustainable products. Still, regulators must take account of the fact that there is the need for a transition phase where “less worse” materials are needed to shift the social system to a new normal. Policies must facilitate the transition towards this new normal rather than restricting environmentally friendlier, non-fossil-based materials before the new normal has been reached.

Another policy instruments to be considered is a quota system for the use of recycled material, which demands that producers incorporate a certain percentage of e.g. recycled plastics or recycled textiles or building materials into their products. The quota itself, and the ramp up of its ambition, however, should consider the availability and quality of recycled material that is available for the satisfaction of the quota requirements. This means that it can only work if the recycling infrastructure also becomes adequately developed and organised.

Similarly, quota systems may also be introduced for bio-based carbon content. Building on the above recommendation, it is suggested to implement sustainability criteria for biomass to be eligible for to bio-based quota. While mandatory sustainability requirements are readily implemented for energy applications (i.e., EU RED), bio-based materials and products are excluded from this regulatory framework. As such, following the RED, a Renewable Materials Directive is called for to be applicable to all non-food biomass uses (and may also be extended to biomass for food and feed). A major benefit of such a directive is that well-designed sustainability criteria, including prioritisation of circular and cascading use principles, will allow for the better use of the biomass readily produced and reduce the land use (change) related GHG emissions. Certification schemes and labels can be used by producers of biomass to demonstrate compliance with these sustainability criteria. In turn, the Green Claims Directive will be key in ensuring the transparency and trustworthiness of sustainability claims.

When focusing on instruments that particularly focus on carbon sequestration, it is worth mentioning the CRCF Regulation, which is a forthcoming EU regulation designed to establish a robust, transparent, and harmonised system for certifying high-quality carbon removals across Europe. Although it targets a wide range of carbon removal strategies in all sectors, including agriculture and forestry, the CRCF also acknowledges carbon storage in long-lasting products and

materials. It is therefore a valuable instrument to link carbon farming and forestry and the circular bioeconomy, allowing carbon captured on the land to be stored within industrial value chains, particularly in bio-based construction, packaging, and biomaterials.

Lastly, one cannot emphasise enough the need for continued policy support, combined with private investments, for R&D in technological advancement, bringing sustainable solutions to markets, introducing targeted subsidies, grants and loans and stimulating education and wider awareness raising. Investment in R&D is crucial to make technological advancements to support transitions to a more circular and sustainable economy at different geographic scales, from global to local. Programs for education and information sharing in relation to (un)sustainable consumer and production practices will help foster consumer demand and industry-wide alignment with circular principles and provide explanations about the benefits of recycled and bio-based products and circularity in general. For instance, expanding climate change education programs and leveraging NGOs and economic actors' collaboration bodies to promote recycling and sustainable consumption practices can further engage citizens and create a culture of sustainability.

Finally, efforts should be undertaken that assess policy impacts across multiple DGs at EU level. Such an "overarching regulatory effort" might be the starting point to close gaps in regulation that are meant to foster a bio-based sector. This would be immensely beneficial to policymakers and producers alike and hold the potential to generate synergies across policy spaces. Lastly, this effort must acknowledge the fact that every decision is a trade-off, which becomes evident when thinking about the allocation of bio-based materials towards specific use cases. This is because there are simply not enough materials to satisfy all demand, which makes concepts like carbon efficiency even more important.

REFERENCES

- Akinsemolu, A., Idowu, A., & Onyeaka, H. (2024). Recycling technologies for biopolymers: Current challenges and future directions. *Polymers*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym16192770>
- Bardy, J., Dürig, T., Lee, P., & Li, J.-X. (2017). Polymer properties and characterization. In Y. Qiu, Y. Chen, G. Zhang, L. Yu, & R. Mantri (Eds.), *Developing solid oral dosage forms* (2nd ed., pp. 181-223). Elsevier Inc.
- Barreca, F., Gabarron, A. M., Yepes, J. F., & Pérez, J. J. P. (2019). Innovative use of giant reed and cork residues for panels of buildings in Mediterranean area. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 140, 259-266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2018.10.005>
- Bennai, F., Ferroukhi, M. Y., Benmahiddine, F., Belarbi, R., & Nouviaire, A. (2022). Assessment of hygrothermal performance of hemp concrete compared to conventional building materials at overall building scale. *Construction and Building Materials*, 316, 126007. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conbuildmat.2021.126007>
- Carus, M., Porc, O., vom Berg, C., Kempen, M., Schier, F., & Tandetzki, J. (2025). Is there enough biomass to defossilise the chemicals and derived materials sector by 2050? nova-Institut GmbH.
- CEFIC. (2024). 2024 Facts and figures of the European chemical industry. <https://cefic.org/a-pillar-of-the-european-economy/facts-and-figures-of-the-european-chemical-industry/>
- CIRFS. (2025). World production by fibre. <https://www.cirfs.org/statistics/key-statistics/world-production-fibre>
- Dutch Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management. (2020, October 16). Duurzaamheidskader biogrondstoffen. <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/documenten/kamerstukken/2020/10/16/duurzaamheidskader-biogrondstoffen>
- Escobar, N., Haddad, S., Börner, J., & Britz, W. (2018). Land use mediated GHG emissions and spillovers from increased consumption of bioplastics. *Environmental Research Letters*, 13(12), 125005. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aaeafb>
- European Commission. (2018). Biomass production, supply, uses and flows in the European Union - First results from an integrated assessment (Camia, A., Robert, N., Jonsson, R., Pilli, R., et al.). Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/539520>
- European Commission. (2020). A Renovation Wave for Europe - Greening our buildings, creating jobs, improving lives (COM(2020) 662 final).
- European Commission. (2020). Chemicals strategy for sustainability - Towards a toxic-free environment. https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/chemicals-strategy_en
- European Commission. (2022). Commission staff working document: Towards a sustainable built environment (SWD(2022) 14 final).
- European Commission. (2023). Transition pathway for the chemical industry. <https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/54595>
- European Environmental Agency. (2023). Managing the systemic use of chemicals in Europe (Briefing). <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/managing-the-systemic-use-of>

- European Environmental Agency. (2024). The destruction of returned and unsold textiles in Europe's circular economy (Briefing No. 01/2024). <https://doi.org/10.2800/752>
- Eurostat. (2021). Waste statistics - Statistics Explained. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- Eurostat. (2024). Production and consumption of chemicals by hazard class. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ENV_CHMHAZ
- Futero. (n.d.). The company: Futero, leads the way to a better, sustainable future. <https://www.futero.com/>
- Green European Foundation. (2017). A strategy for biobased economy. https://gef.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/A_strategy_for_a_biobased_economy.pdf
- GVR. (2024). Cellulose acetate market size, share & growth report, 2030. <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/cellulose-acetate-market-report#>
- Hanke, G., Walvoort, D., Ruiz-Orejón, L. F., van Loon, W. M., Giorgetti, A., Molina-Jack, M. E., & Vinci, M. (2025). European coastline macro litter trends 2015-2021. European Commission, Joint Research Centre. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/5cfaf1c0-e50d-11ef-bc1c-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>
- James, B., Sun, Y., Pate, K., Shankar, R., Izallalen, M., Mazumder, S., ... Ward, C. (2024a). Foaming enables material-efficient bioplastic products with minimal persistence. *ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering*, 12, 16030-16040. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.4c05822>
- James, B., Ward, C., Hahn, M., Thrope, S., & Reddy, C. (2024b). Minimizing the environmental impacts of plastic pollution through ecodesign of products with low environmental persistence. *ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering*, 12, 1185-1194. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acssuschemeng.3c05534>
- Kidder Maede, R., McCormack, H., Clark, L., Sclater, A., & Lamborn, L. (1905). A monthly journal of practical, applied and analytical chemistry (Vol. 3). *Chemical Engineer*. McCready Publishing.
- Köhler, A., Watson, D., Trzepacz, S., Löw, C., Liu, R., Danneck, J., ... Faraca, G. (2021). Circular economy perspectives in the EU textile sector (EUR 30734 EN). Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2760/858144>
- Kubiwicz, S., & Booth, A. (2017). Biodegradability of plastics: Challenges and misconceptions. *Environmental Science & Technology - Scientific Opinion*, 12058-12060. <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-4702-2210>
- Kwon, S., Zambrano, M., Pawlak, J., & Venditti, R. (2021). Effect of lignocellulosic fiber composition on the aquatic biodegradation of wood pulps and the isolated cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin components: Kinetic modelling of the biodegradation process. *Cellulose*, 28, 2863-2877. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10570-021-03680-6>
- Le, D. L., Salomone, R., Nguyen, Q. T. (2024). Sustainability assessment methods for circular bio-based building materials: A literature review. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 352, 120137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2024.120137>
- McDonough, K., Itrich, N., Casteel, K., Manzies, J., Williams, T., Krivos, K., & Price, J. (2017). Assessing the biodegradability of microparticles disposed down the drain. *Chemosphere*, 452-458. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2017.02.091>

- OECD. (2022). Global plastics outlook: Economic drivers, environmental impacts and policy options. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/de747aef-en>
- OECD. (2022). Global plastic waste set to almost triple by 2060, says OECD [Press release]. <https://www.oecd.org/en/about/news/press-releases/2022/06/global-plastic-waste-set-to-almost-triple-by-2060.html>
- Plonka, M. (2023). Greater responsibility in lieu of “fast fashion.” *Academia: The Magazine of the Polish Academy of Sciences*, 38-41.
- Sahimaa, O., Miller, E. M., Halme, M., Niinimäki, K., Tanner, H., Mäkelä, M., ... Hummel, M. (2023). The only way to fix fast fashion is to end it. *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment*, 4(3), 137-138.
- Schützenberger, P. (1865). Action de l'acide acétique anhydre sur la cellulose, l'amidon, les sucres, la mannite et ses congénères, les glucosides et certaines matières colorantes végétales. *Comptes rendus hebdomadaires des séances de l'Académie des sciences*.
- Sebruyns, L., Van de Perre, D., & Hölter, D. (2024). Biodegradability of cellulose diacetate in aqueous environments. *Journal of Polymers and the Environment*, 32, 1326-1341.
- Slezak, R., Krzystek, L., Puchalski, M., Krucińska, I., & Sitarski, A. (2023). Degradation of biobased film plastics in soil under natural conditions. *Science of the Total Environment*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.161401>
- Statista. (2025). Plastics use in the European Union in 2019, with projections to 2060. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1341408/european-union-plastics-use-outlook/>
- Systemiq. (2022). Planet positive chemicals: Pathways for the chemical industry to enable a sustainable global economy. <https://www.systemiq.earth/wp-content/uploads/2022/09/Main-report-v1.20-2.pdf>
- Teixeira, M., Paiva, M., Amorim, M., & Felgueiras, H. (2020). Electrospun nanocomposites containing cellulose and its derivatives modified with specialized biomolecules for an enhanced wound healing. *Nanomaterials*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano10030557>
- Teixeira, S., Assis Silva, R., de Oliveira, T., Stringheta, P., Ribeiro Pinto, M., & Ferreira Soares, N. (2021). Glycerol and triethyl citrate plasticizer effects on molecular, thermal, mechanical, and barrier properties of cellulose acetate films. *Food Bioscience*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fbio.2021.101202>
- Textile Exchange. (2023). Materials market report 2023. <https://textileexchange.org>
- Wolfs, J., & Meier, M. (2021). A more sustainable synthesis approach for cellulose acetate using the DBU/CO₂ switchable solvent system. *Green Chemistry*, 23, 4410-4420. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1GC01508G>
- Yu, Y., & Flury, M. (2024). Unlocking the potentials of biodegradable plastics with proper management and evaluation at environmentally relevant concentrations. *Materials Sustainability*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44296-024-00012-0>

APPENDIX 1 OVERVIEW TYPE OF POLICY INSTRUMENTS

In terms of policy instruments nature, the following 6 types can be distinguished:

1. **Direct regulation** - a command and control approach using mandatory standards and licences that require people/companies/market actors to change their behaviour and penalise them if they are found to be non-compliant. Examples of direct regulatory instruments in the bioeconomy include quotas, mandates, product standards, targets (quotas addressing government/economic sectors), green procurement rules and permitting and zoning instruments (e.g. territorial instrument such as drink water protection area or Nitrogen sensitive area). We also include here eligibility criteria such as biomass sustainability criteria in the EU-Renewable Energy Directive.
2. **Economic instruments** - includes all instruments that change incentives (taxes, subsidies), but also quantity restrictions ((tradable) quota, tariff rate quota), and charges. These instruments provide incentives for people to change their behaviour voluntarily (e.g. based on their own rational cost-benefit calculations). So it includes all instruments that leave the decision about resource uses in the hands of market participants while changing prices for using a resource. Price changes can be induced directly via taxes, fees, charges, subsidies etc. or indirectly via tradeable permits.
3. **Voluntary approaches** - could include codes of good practice, self-regulation and other industry-led initiatives. Financial incentive schemes could be part of these instruments. These approaches typically encourage rather than force people or companies to adopt the desired behaviour. The voluntary carbon market is an example.
4. **Information and advice sharing systems or information instruments** - measure to raise awareness education and facilitate changes in behaviour.-
5. **Market-based signalling approaches** - labelling, traceability, voluntary certification schemes and farm assurance schemes. These approaches are often related to informational problems (lack of information about product quality and food safety) hindering the proper functioning of markets;
6. **Other measures/instruments** not in the categories above such as platforms for collaboration, behavioural influencing instruments (e.g. to prevent nudging).

APPENDIX 2 OVERVIEW OF PRINCIPLES OF THE CIRCULAR BIO-BASED ECONOMY TO WHICH POLICY INSTRUMENTS CAN CONTRIBUTE

In the Sustrack deliverable 5.1 (Elbersen and Schindler, 2024) a description was given of Circular Bio-based Economy concept and how it is linked in setting policy priorities. These policy are summarized underneath and are used to classify the policy instruments recommended per sector in chapters 2, 3 and 4.

Principles of the CBBE which can be aimed at in policy instruments:

- 1) **The reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions:** The CBBE is not a panacea for all sustainability challenges, but it clearly contributes to an economy with net-zero GHG emissions. This also requires a consideration of GHG emissions or emissions savings related to biomass and land use in a society that increasingly relies on using biomass. While it can be argued that all biomass-related challenges, such as sustainable agriculture and food security policies, are part of the CBBE transition, Sustrack emphasises the focus on substituting fossil resources and a climate-friendly biomass use, as this helps to find solutions to remaining policy gaps and avoids copying existing policy agendas. With regard to fossil resources, this also implies a focus on the substitution of resources for material uses, rather than energy uses, to avoid replicating already developed climate policy solutions in the energy sector.
- 2) The second principle, **resource use efficiency**, contributes to the CBBE objectives in at least three important ways. First, efficient resource use reduces the overall costs of the transformation and thus contributes to the acceptance of transformative policies. Second, efficient resource use contributes to environmental goals by reducing pressures of the bio-based parts of the economy on nature, because efficiency implies minimising the resources that are necessary to satisfy a given demand, and all related environmental damages from resource cultivation or extraction. Third, the principle of resource use efficiency can provide guidance for dealing with contradictions and trade-offs between different CBBE objectives. For example, carbon recycling can help to reduce GHG emissions, but the amount of energy and chemicals required in recycling processes imply possible trade-offs with energy- or environmental targets [3, 4]. The efficiency criterion can be used to guide an appropriate level of recycling by balancing the benefits and (resource) costs of these processes [5].
- 3) The third principle, **decoupling resource use from economic growth**, ensures that resource efficiency and emissions reduction effectively contribute to limiting resource consumption and pollution [e.g., 9]. It specifically addresses objectives such as sustainable resource management and supply security. The decoupling principle accounts for the challenge that, even with increased resource efficiency and a phase-out of fossil fuels, resource depletion and pollution still could reach problematic proportions, for example in the form of biodiversity losses or a shortage of critical raw materials. While concepts like “green growth” include hopes of reaching decoupling simply by increasing efficiency, empirical evidence does not provide broad support for this thesis so far [9, 10]. In general, the efficiency principle is more about optimising the use of a given amount of resources, and does not necessarily limit the total quantity of resource extraction, required imports or pollution. For example, increasing resource efficiency through more recycling may well reduce the amount of virgin resources required to produce a single product. However, in regard to the entire economy and the related total resource consumption, even high degrees of (resource efficient) recycling can be associated with a growing demand for primary resources [6]. Possible reasons include that increasing demand for production

inputs from economic growth outpaces the growing supply of recycled (secondary) materials. Another reason could be that recycling processes themselves require a growing amount of primary resources as input. Consequently, recycling or other efficiency-related measures may not be sufficient to reduce import dependencies of a growing economy. Second, in regard to decoupling economic growth and pollution or environmental degradation, simply substituting the current levels of fossil resource use with biomass, according to principle 1, might lead to (or aggravate) unsustainable levels of natural capital consumption (e.g., biodiversity loss). While traditional environmental and climate policies already address this second challenge to some extent, the frequent mentions of decoupling in CBBE related documents reveal that it is often considered necessary to include increased efforts or additional policy tools to limit overall resource consumption and pollution in a CBBE policy agenda.

Project Consortium

